

3rd Annual Meeting of the PAS-AGRO-PAS project

12-13 May 2026

Attendees (partner leaders or representing partner leaders): Vasco Cadavez (VC), Ursula Gonzales-Barron (UGB), Hamza Tami (HT), Jose Manuel Lorenzo (JL), Raul Bodas (RB), Halima Elhatmi (HE)

Online attendees: Ouranios Tzamaloukas (OT), Abdelillah Araba (AA), Fabien Stark (FS), Antonello Cannas (AC)

On days 1 and 2, the presentation ran similar to scheduled. OT delivered his presentation on day 1, while AA, AC and FS delivered their presentations on day 2. No presentation was done by the APRI partner.

At the end of the meeting, the following actions were proposed:

Responsible institution	Actions	Deadline
ECoE	For preparing the deliverable D3.2, partners should email results on crop productivity to ECoE to compile	30 th September
	Partners should send information on any models for pastures, forages, or crops to ECoE for them to compile D3.5	30 th September
	ECoE to send results summary on the efficacy of strategies on animal productivity and carcass quality to APRI for them to compile D4.4	30 th October
	Quality of milk post-intervention in comparison to control. Send results summary to CTC to compile D5.5	30 th October
ITACYL	Send summary on agronomic results to ECoE	30 th September
	Send summary results on quality of products to CTC to compile D5.5	30 th October
	ITACYL will compile D4.3 on animal health and welfare	30 th November

CTC	Results on the efficacy of strategies on animal productivity and carcass quality must be sent to APRI	30 th October
	CTC will compile D5.3 on quality of newly developed functional foods. Therefore, all involved partners must send their summaries in due time	30 th October
	CTC will compile D 5.5 on quality of agropastoral products post-intervention. Therefore all involved partners must send their summaries in due time.	30 th October
IAV	IAV will compile the report on the efficacy of strategies on forage productivity/quality (D3.5). Request results summary from all involved partners	30 th November
UIZ	Send research results on biometry, sensing and animal activity to ITACYL to compile D4.3	30 th November
	Results summary on camel milk kefir must be sent to CTC	30 th October
	Results summary on newly developed functional foods must be sent to CTC	30 th October
	Results on LAB characterisation must be sent to IRA for the compilation of the bank of bacteriocinogenic LABs	15 th December
UNISS	Send summarised results of the work on dual-purpose use of cereals to ECoE for the compilation of D3.2.	30 th September
	Send summarised results of the work on predictive models for lupin and faba beans to ECoE for the compilation of D3.5	30 th September
	Send summarised results on smart reader to ITACYL for the compilation of D4.3	30 th October
	Send summarised results on the strategies to improve milk production to APRI for compilation of D4.4	30 th November
	Send summarised results of Fruhe cheese quality to CTC for D5.5	30 th September

	Request results from involved partners for the compilation of the deliverables of WP6	30 th January 2027
IRA	IRA must develop a metadata format for compiling the information of the bacteriocinogenic LABs	30 th October
	Send results summary of post-intervention quality of products and functional foods to CTC for compilation of D5.3 and D5.5.	30 th September
	Send information to Vasco for updating the website about the multistakeholders workshop	30 th June
	Results of SWOT analysis, send to UNISS for the elaboration of D6.2.	30 th September
	Send summarised results of profitability study of camel and goat milk to UNISS for the compilation of D6.1	30 th September
	Share the protocols or methodologies to conduct the profitability study with all the partners, so that they all can follow the same method	30 th June
SELMET	Case study coordinators must complete the D5.6 proposal for the notebook of quality standards, made by Noziere-Petit, so that deliverable is completed	30 th June
	SELMET to request any further information for D4.5 (predictive models for enhanced management of local herds), in order to conduct simulations	30 th July
	SELMET's deadline for receiving all info towards D4.5	30 th October

ACTIONS FOR COMMUNICATION/DISSEMINATION EVENTS OR PUBLICATIONS

- **Local meetings, local seminars, workshops, exchange of students:** send short news and photo(s) to UIZ to update the social media
- **Conference abstracts, conference proceedings:** send PDFs to Vasco to upload on Zenodo.
- **Peer-reviewed articles:** inform Vasco and Ursula when a new paper has been published. Also UIZ to prepare a news on social media

UPCOMING MEETINGS

- 1) Online meeting with APRI should be organised in order to determine the situation of advances and deliverables that APRI should compile and integrate in due time. Vasco to send out doodle to meet in June.
- 2) Online meeting for IPB, UIZ and IRA to delineate the deliverable of the bank of bacteriocinogenic LABs. Metadata and extension of information to be decided. Vasco to send out doodle to meet in July.

Presentations follow.

Update, work towards deliverables, communication/dissemination activities

Ass. Prof. Ouranios Tzamaloukas
Eratosthenes Center of Excellence (ECoE)
 Department of Agricultural Sciences,
 Biotechnology and Food Science
Cyprus University of Technology

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The Making of Fragile Agro-ecosystems Productive, Adaptive and Sustainable: Multifunctional Agro-pastoralism (PAS-AGRO-PAS)

Contact person /PI

Ass. Prof. Ouranios Tzamaloukas
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WP that we are participating

Fig. 2: Workpackages (WP) of the PAS-AGRO-PAS project

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WP N°	1	Lead beneficiary					IPB				
WP title	Management and coordination										
Participant N°	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
Short name	IPB	ECoE	APRI	SELMET	MoSAR	UNISS	IAV	UIZ	CTC	ITACyL	IRA
PM/ participant	6	2	3	2.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	1.5	1	0.5	0.5
Start month	1				End month				36		

Deliverables

D1.1: The “PAS-AGRO-PAS Pack of Methods”: methods for on-farm experiments, essays (DEM, CO; M8)

D1.2: The full “PAS-AGRO-PAS Pack of Methods”: plus modelling methods (DEM, CO; M28)

WP1: management we have employed several researchers/students in the project and participated in those reports prepared by Vasco and Ursula

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WP N°	2	Lead beneficiary					SELMET				
WP title	Diagnosis of the agro-ecosystem/socio-economic traits of the agro-pastoral production systems										
Participant N°	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
Short name	IPB	ECoE	APRI	SELMET	MoSAR	UNISS	IAV	UIZ	CTC	ITACyL	IRA
PM/participant	17.45	5	8	9.9	13.4	3	8	12	1	2	2
Start month	1				End month			15			

Deliverables

D2.1: Common conceptual model of agro-pastoral production systems in interaction with their surrounding environment (**DEM, PU**; Month 4)

D2.2: Resource allocation models for current agro-pastoral production systems (**DEM, PU**; Month 10)

D2.3: Agro-ecosystem health assessments of the agro-pastoral production systems (**R, PU**; Month 10)

D2.4: Transversal analysis of farms characterisation (agro-pastoral system and SWOT) to identify common patterns and prototypes of strategy for the studied agro-pastoral farming systems (**R, PU**; Month 15)

Task 2.4: SWOT analysis of current situations (M10-M15) (Lead: **MoSAR**; Participants: IPB, ECoE, APRI, SELMET, UNISS, IAV, UIZ, ITACyL, CTC, IRA)

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D2.4: Transversal analysis of farms characterization (agro-pastoral system and SWOT) to identify common patterns and prototypes of strategy for the studied agro-pastoral farming systems

1. Introduction

Sheep and goat farming is a well-established and highly important activity of the primary production sector in the Mediterranean region. It is a significant provider of income, employment, environmental protection, and social cohesion in many Mediterranean countries (de Rancourt et al., 2006). Long-term historical, geopolitical and socioeconomic changes in addition to production trait selection by farmers over the years, formed the characteristics of the traditional sheep and goat farming in Cyprus and elsewhere, including the variety of animal breeds and genotypes that are being raised under these production systems in the area, providing an important source of income for the farmers (Boyazoglu & Morand-Fehr, 2001; de Rancourt et al., 2006). This traditional way of farming has resulted in a wide range of authentic, rustic products with high tradition, such as halloumi cheese, with exceptional organoleptic characteristics, that are highly preferred by the consumers (Toromujica et al., 2015; Koutsoukis et al., 2017; Pappa et al., 2022).

Today, despite the products' high popularity and demand and the general recognition of the role that the small ruminant farming systems play for the preservation of the environment and the social and economic development in the rural areas, their sustainability is challenged by several overhanging factors, such as the high costs of production, purchase of animal feeds,

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Leading / Contribution to WP3

WP N°	3		Lead beneficiary					ECoE				
WP title	Enhanced productivity, adaptiveness and diversification of crops, pastures, forages											
Participant N°	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	
Short name	IPB	ECoE	APRI	SELMET	MoSAR	UNISS	IAV	UIZ	CTC	ITACyL	IRA	
PM/participant	15.65	8	9	4.9	2.2	8	10	11.4	1	3	11	
Start month	3					End month			30			

The are three main pillars or targets of this WP :

- Task 3.1 / 3.2 / 3.3 Strategies to enhanced productivity, adaptiveness and diversification of crops, pastures, forages
- Task 3.4 Agro-byproducts as animal feeds
- Task 3.5 Predictive models for pastures, forages and crop productivities

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Comparative Forage 2024/2025 and 2025/2026

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General Information about the experiments for 2 consecutive years

In this slide is about to explain the procedures that have been carried out so far (soil sampling soil preparation, fertilization, sowing) regarding the research project PAS-AGRO-PAS and growing plants mixes to compare them

For **the first year** Cultivated in three different locations in Cyprus, with different characteristics for example rainfall, 14 plants mixtures for the purpose of comparing them

Plants used: Common wheat(*Triticum aestivum*), Ryegrass(*Lolium multiflorum*), Triticale(x *Triticale*), Oats(*Avena sativa*), Barley(*Hordeum vulgare*), Vetch(*Vicia sativa*), Pea(*Pisum sativum*), Cyprus vetch(*Lathyrus ochrus*), Balansa clover(*Medicago polymorpha*), Bur Clover(*Trifolium michelianum*).

For **the second year** Cultivated in three same locations with first year in Cyprus, with different characteristics for example rainfall, 17 plant mixtures in Athalassa and 10 plant mixture in Kivisili and Acheliafor with the purpose to compare them

Plants used: Common wheat(*Triticum aestivum*), Ryegrass(*Lolium multiflorum*), Triticale(x *Triticale*), Oats(*Avena sativa*), Barley(*Hordeum vulgare*), Vetch(*Vicia sativa*), Pea(*Pisum sativum*), Cyprus vetch(*Lathyrus ochrus*), Balansa clover(*Medicago polymorpha*), Bur Clover(*Trifolium michelianum*), Sulla (*Hedysarum coronarium*), Barley(*Hordeum vulgare*)

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Map of Cyprus with the locations

Experimental areas:

- Kivisili Larnaka,
- Athalassa Nicosia,
- Achelia Pafos

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Maps of compared the rainfall in different years at the same month(December)

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Average temperature of the experimental areas 2024,2025,2026 and comparison with the period 1981-2010

	1981-2010			2024			2025			2026		
	ATH*	KIV**	ACH***	ATH	KIV	ACH	ATH	KIV	ACH	ATH	KIV	ACH
September	26,2	25,3	24	27,0	27	26,2	27,7	27,1	25,9			
October	21,8	22,2	21,4	22,2	23,3	22,9	22,1	23,3	22,1			
November	16,2	17,5	17,6	16,6	18,6	18,7	19,6	21,5	20,8			
December	12,1	13,9	14,4	15,1	15,1	15,5	13,3	16,1	16,3			
January	10,4	12,1	12,7	12,8	14,9	15,2	12,3	14,9	14,8	10,6	13,6	14,0
February	10,6	12	12,6	12,7	14,5	14,5	9,4	11,5	11,8	15,3	14,5	15,4
March	13	13,9	13,7	15,0	16,6	16,5	15,9	17,3	16,6	14,8	14,1	15,0
April	17,4	17,2	16,5	21,3	21,1	20,2		18,5	17,6	17,9	17,1	17,8
May	22,2	21	19,6	22,8	22,5	21,6	17,9	22,2	21,1			
June	26,5	24,8	22,8	31,4	28,8	27	23,1	26,5	24,6			
July	29,6	27,2	25,2	32,3	30,2	28,4	28,7	29,2	27,4			
August	29,4	27,6	25,8	30,9	29,2	28,3	31,5	29,6	27,7			
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*ATH= ATHALASSA **KIV= KIVISILI ***ACH=ACHELIA

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Precipitation table of the experimental areas in the years 2024, 2025,2026 compared to the average for the period 1981-2010

	1981-2010			2024			2025			2026		
	ATH*	KIV**	ACH***	ATH	KIV	ACH	ATH	KIV	ACH	ATH	KIV	ACH
September	12,2	4,3	3,6	33,6	8,6	0,8	Nil	Nil	Nil			
October	20,7	16	27,4	Nil	Nil	Nil	1,5	9,2	35,6			
November	43,2	46,8	52,6	45,0	63	76,1	17,5	15,4	17,4			
December	57,8	90,1	79	71,4	91,8	158,3	83,3	108,8	93,7			
January	48,8	73,7	78,8	92,5	86,6	82,5	9,7	8,6	30,6	85,7	93,4	96,9
February	44,5	50,3	59,8	18,4	34	35,3	28,3	13	34,3	27,2	58,4	36,7
March	31,9	35,8	34,4	54,5	13,8	34,4	12	9,8	5,4	54,6	79,2	78,4
April	19,1	14,2	15,5	96,9	17,8	0,7	8,3	7,2	20	33,4	55,1	47,8
May	24,6	9,8	6,1	19,8	16,2	11	44,2	2	15,3			
June	11,6	2	1,3	0,2	0,8	Nil	Nil	1,4	0,2			
July	4,2	0,5	0,2	0,1	0,6	Nil	3,7	0,6	Nil			
August	1,8	0,3	0	2,0	0,2	Nil	Nil	0,2	Nil			
Total(Nov-Mar)	226,2	296,7	304,6	279,5								
Total	320,4	343,8	358,7	432,1	333	399,1						

*ATH=ATHALASSA **KIV=KIVISILI ***ACH=ACHELIA

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Some pictures of the seeds tested

1.Common wheat

Origin: Greece

Variety: Gogas

Greek name: Σιτάρι

Scientific name:Triticum aestivum L

4.Common wheat- Ryegrass(60-40 MIX)

Greece

Σιτάρι μαλακό- Λόλιο

Triticum aestivumL-Wester Wondicum

2.Ryegrass

Greece

Dukat

Λόλιο

Lolium multiflorum

5. SUPERFIVE (Mixture 5 varieties)

Greece

Mixture: Barley (Hordeum vulgare), Oats

(AvenasativaL), Vetch(Vicia sativa),

Pea(Pisum Sativum),Triticale

Κριθάρι, Βρώμη, Βίκος, Μπιζέλι,

Τριτικάλε

3.Common wheat- Triticale (50-50 MIX)

Greece

Catria-Dodoni

Σιτάρι μαλακό-Τριτικάλε

Triticum aestivumL-Triticale spp.

6. Fine (Mixture 6 varieties)

Greece

Mixture:Barley(Hordeum vulgare), Oat

((Avenasativa L), Vetch(Viciasativa),

Pea(Pisum Sativum),Ryegrass (Wester

Wondicum) Triticale

Κριθάρι, Βρώμη, Βίκος, Μπιζέλι,

Τριτικάλε,Λόλιο

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7. Vetch

Cyprus
Vicia sativa
Βίκος

11.VCU-BW V.4(Wheat)

Cyprus
***new variety**
Μαλακό σιτάρι

8. Cyprus vetch

Cyprus
Lathirus ochrus
Λούβανα

12.Triticale

Cyprus
Triticale spp.
Τριτικάλε

9.Bur clove

Italy
Medicago polymorpha
Μηδική

13. Common Wheat- Grass Pea (Mixture 50-50)

Cyprus
Triticum aestivum L-Lathirus spp
Τριτικάλε- Λουβάνα

10. Balance Clove

Italy
Trifolium Michellanum
Τριφύλλι

14 Common Wheat- Vetch (Mix 50-50)

Cyprus
Triticum aestivum L-Vicia sativa
Μαλακό σιτάρι- Βίκος

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Table of treatments 2024-2025

OBS	SEED SOURCR 2023/24	NAME OF VARIETY	KG/DA	G/PLOT(16,8 m2)
1	COMMON WHEAT	GOGAS(IMPORTED FROM GREECE)	20.000	336g
2	RYEGRASS	DUKAT (WESTER WONDICUM)(IMPORTED FROM GREECE)	12.000	202g
3	TRITICALE/COMMON WHEAT(50/50)	CATRIA/DODONI(IMPORTED FROM GREECE)	20.000	336g
4	COMMON WHEAT/RYEGRASS(60/40)	IMPORTED FROM GREECE	20.000	336g(202-134)
5	TRITICALE.OATS.BARLEY.VETCH.PEA	SUPERFIVE (IMPORTED FROM GREECE)	20.000	336g
6	TRITICALE.OATS.BARLEY.VETCH.PEA RYEGRASS	FIENO (IMPORTED FROM GREECE)	20.000	336g
7	VETCH(Vicia sativa)	ARISTOU LOCAL	15.000	252g
8	CYPRUS VETCH(Lathyrus ochrus)	ARISTOU LOCAL	15.000	252g
9	BUR CLOVER (Meticago polymorpha)	IMPORTED FROM ITALY	5.000	84g
10	BALANSA CLOVER (Trifolium michelianum)	IMPORTED FROM ITALY	5.000	84g
11	VCU-BW V.4(WHEAT NEW VARIETY)	LOCAL	20.000	336g
12	TRITICALE	ACHERITU LOCAL	20.000	336g
13	COMMON WHEAT/CYPRUS VETCH (50/50)	LOCAL	20.000	336g(104-232)
14	COMMON WHEAT/VETCH (50/50)	LOCAL	20.000	336g(154-182)

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Table of treatments in Athalassa 2025-2026

OBS	SEED SOURCR 2023/24	NAME OF VARIETY	KG/DA	g/PLOT(13,65 m2)
1	COMMON WHEAT	GOGAS(IMPORTED FROM GREECE)	20.000	273g
2	TRITICALE	RTG COPLAC (IMPORTED FROM ITALY)	20.000	273g
3	TRITICALE/COMMON WHEAT(50/50)	CATRIA/DODONI (IMPORTED FROM GREECE)	20.000	273g
4	TRITICALE	PIETRARSA(IMPORTED FROM ITALY)	20.000	273g
5	TRITICALE.OATS.BARLEY.VETCH.PEA	SUPERFIVE (IMPORTED FROM GREECE)	20.000	273g
6	TRITICALE.OATS.BARLEY.VETCH.PEA RYEGRASS	FIENO (IMPORTED FROM GREECE)	20.000	273g
7	BARLEY	SY CHASKA (IMPORTED FROM ITALY)	20.000	273g
8	BARLEY	LG ROSELLA (IMPORTED FROM ITALY)	20.000	273g
9	BUR CLOVER (Meticago polymorpha)	IMPORTED FROM ITALY	5.000	68g
10	BARLEY	LEANDRA (IMPRORTED FROM ITALY)	20.000	273g
11	VCU-BW V.4(WHEAT NEW VARIETY)	LOCAL	20.000	273g
12	TRITICALE	ACHERITU LOCAL	20.000	273g
13	COMMON WHEAT/Cyprus Vetch(50/50)	LOCAL	20.000	273g(85g-188g)
14	COMMON WHEAT/VETCH (50/50)	LOCAL	20.000	273g(125g-148g)
15	COMMON WHEAT	MONALISA (IMPORTED FROM ITALY)	20.000	273g
16	BARLEY	LG ZORIKA (IMPORTED FROM ITALY)	20.000	273g
17	Sulla (Hedysarum coronarium)	IMPORTED FROM ITALY	5.000	68g

*only in Athalassa field sowing all the OBS, in fields of Kivisili and Achelia we dont sowing the OBS: 2, 4, 7, 8, 10, 15, 16

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Table of samples in Achelia & Kivisili 2025-2026

OBS	SEED SOURCR 2023/24	NAME OF VARIETY	KG/DA	g/PLOT(13,65 m2)
1	COMMON WHEAT	GOGAS(IMPORTED FROM GREECE)	20.000	273g
3	TRITICALE/COMMON WHEAT(50/50)	CATRIA/DODONI (IMPORTED FROM GREECE)	20.000	273g
5	TRITICALE.OATS.BARLEY.VETCH.PEA	SUPERFIVE (IMPORTED FROM GREECE)	20.000	273g
6	TRITICALE.OATS.BARLEY.VETCH.PEA RYEGRASS	FIENO (IMPORTED FROM GREECE)	20.000	273g
9	BUR CLOVER (Meticago polymorpha)	IMPORTED FROM ITALY	5.000	68g
11	VCU-BW V.4(WHEAT NEW VARIETY)	LOCAL	20.000	273g
12	TRITICALE	ACHERITOY LOCAL	20.000	273g
13	COMMON WHEAT/Cyprus Vetch(50/50)	LOCAL	20.000	273g(85g-188g)
14	COMMON WHEAT/VETCH (50/50)	LOCAL	20.000	273g(125g-148g)
17	Sulla (Hedysarum coronarium)	IMPORTED FROM ITALY	5.000	68g

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Soil preparation and separation of experimental plots

Year 2024-2025

Number of pieces: 14

Number of repetitions: 2

Soil preparation is necessary so that we achieve the appropriate conditions in the soil for the sporocline

Year 2025-2026

Number of pieces: 17 in Athalassa, 10 in Kivisili and Achelia

Number of repetitions: 2

Soil preparation is necessary so that we achieve the appropriate conditions in the soil for the sporocline

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Fertilization and soil sampling

For the season 2024-2025 fertilization and soil sampling were carried out during the week of 11/11-17/11

For the season 2025-2026 and fertilization and soil sampling were carried out in 30/11/2025 in Athalassa and in week 23-30/12/2025 in Achelia and Kivisili.

Followed fertilization for both seasons:

In sowing: 20(N)-20(P)-0(K)20Kg/daa

- *In Kivisili area we applied 40 fertilization Kg/da(AΥΤΟ ΜΠΟΡΕΙ ΝΑ ΒΓΕΙ)

Fertilization depth: approx. 5 cm

A fertilization machine was used for pollution

We taken 3 randomly samples(all closely to center places to avoiding the extreme pieces)

from field, which the first 5 cm are removed and taken the next 5cm for sampling.

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Pictures of fertilization and Sowing

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Sowing crops

Season 2024-2025

The sowing of the selected areas was carried out from 21/11 to 11/12 in the morning hours (9:30-10:30AM) following the data below

Design: Randomized Complete Block and 2 replications were performed, to enhance the reliability of the experiment

Sowing plot: 6 rows X 0.175m X 16m = 16.80 m²

Harvest plot: 6 rows X 0.175m X 15m = 15.75m²

* Around the crop, we sowing common wheat, of their own variety, to protect the crop and for competition

A sowing machine was used for sowing

Season 2025-2026

The sowing of the selected areas was carried out in 30/11/2025 in Athalassa, 30/12/2025 in Achelia and 05/02/2026 in Kivisili in the morning hours (9:30-10:30AM). Lots of rainfalls in Kivisili area they didn't allow earlier sowing. The data we are follow are:

Design: Randomized Complete Block and 2 replications were performed, to enhance the reliability of the experiment

Sowing plot: 6 rows X 0.175m X 13m = 13.65 m²

Harvest plot: 6 rows X 0.175m X 10m = 12.60m²

* Around the crop, we sowing common wheat, of their own variety, to protect the crop and for competition

A sowing machine was used for sowing

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SEED PLAN ON ACTUAL SCALE (ATHALASSA) season 2024-2025

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ACTUAL SCALE SEED PLAN (KIVISILI) 2024-2025

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SEED PLAN ON ACTUAL SCALE (ACHELIA)season 2024-2025

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SEED PLAN ON ACTUAL SCALE (ATHALASSA) season 2025-2026

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ACTUAL SCALE SEED PLAN (KIVISILI) 2025-2026

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SEED PLAN ON ACTUAL SCALE (ACHELIA) season 2025-2026

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Images from the Sampling and Measuring

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Botanical screening of samples

Figure: Botanical sorting of sample 13 (left: Vetch, right: Common Wheat)

After sampling, botanical sorting of the samples followed in order to remove weeds from the samples, identify the weeds and subsequently weigh the samples to obtain the fresh net weight

All the plants are get be weeds if are finding in another sample field.

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Weed identification

Sonchus oleraceus

Ζοχός

Pisum sativum

Μπιτζέλι

Anthemis tinctoria

Άγριο Μαργαρίτα

Malva sylvestris

Μολόχα

Lamium amplexicaule

δωδεκάνθη

Calystegia sepium

Περικοκλάδα

Erysimum repandum

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Weighing fresh samples

The **fresh matter** of the samples was weighed in order to measure the net weight of the plants and the content (in grams and %) of weeds within the samples

The sample was placed on a precision electronic scale to obtain the net weight. In the case of only one plant in the sample, we will have one measurement, while in the case of more than one plant in the sample, we calculated the net weight of each plant separately.

After each weighing, the sample was placed in aluminum pans and taken to the oven for DM determination. In the oven, the samples were left for 70 hours at 65°C in order to remove moisture and maintain the dry matter.

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Weighing dry matter

After 70 hours, the moisture was removed from the samples (we found this by repeated weighing of the samples), the samples were weighed together with the pans and then transferred to bags that were sealed. The pans were weighed again to obtain the tare weight as well as the bags before their use and were subtracted from the net weight of the DM.

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Protein, NDF and ash determination

- For the determination of protein, 1g of sample was weighed and the Kjeldahl protocol was followed.
- For ash determination, 2g of sample was weighed into porcelain containers and placed in the incinerator at 550°C for 4.30 hours.

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Different stage of development

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Pictures from the treatments crops - forages (season 2024-2025)

1.Common wheat

3.Common wheat- Triticale (50-50 MIX)

2.Ryegrass

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4.Common wheat- Ryegrass(60-40 MIX)

5. SUPERFIVE (Mixture 5 varieties)

6. Fieno (Mixture 6 varieties)

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7. Vetch

11.VCU-BW V.4(Wheat)

8. Cyprus vetch

12.Triticale

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9. Medicago Polymorpha

10. Trifolium Michellianum

13. Common Wheat- Cyprus vetch (Mixture 50-50)

14 Common Wheat- Vetch (Mix 50-50)

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Harvesting of season 2024-2025 and 2025-2026

The harvest was also carried out during the period of 26/3/25 to 2/4/2025 and now May 2026 when the grain of the cereals reached just before the milk stage and the legumes before the formation of the flower.

For the harvest, machines were used that cut the plants at a height of 10cm. The corresponding sampling was carried out from each area as well as the recording of the height and weight of forage.

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Εικόνες από την καταγραφή μετρήσεων ύψους και βάρους χορτονομών

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Soil results.

- All soils can be cultivated without causing a toxicity problem in the crop.
- Alkaline soils, with a pH of 7.9 for Athalassa, 8 for Kivisili and 8.7 for Achelia.
- Based on the % amount of the soils in sand, silt and clay, we classify the three cultivated soils:
 - 1.Athalassa: **clay** (sand 45.7%, silt 28.3%, 26%clay)
 - 2.Kivisili: **sand loam** (71.7% sand, 28.3 silt, 26% clay)
 - 3.Achelia: **clay loam** (sand 45.7%, silt 14.4%, 32% clay)

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SOIL Results

Parameter	ATHALASSA	KIVISILI	ACHELIA
Boron(B) (mg/kg)	0,6	0,3	0,2
Electricalconductivity(EC) (μS/cm)	590	1433	216
Calcium Carbonate(CaCO3) (%)	21	24,6	27,4
Available Nitrogen(N) (mg/kg)	64,4	215	96,3
Available Phosphorus(P) (mg/kg)	7,9	91,5	21,1
Available Potassium(K) (mg/kg)	325	1305	1006
Organic Matter (%)	1	3	1,5
pH	7,9	8	8,7
Clay (%)	26	14	32
Silt (%)	28,3	14,4	14,4
Sand (%)	45,7	71,7	53,7
Magnesium (Mg) (mg/Kg)	844	1791	515
Iron (Fe) (mg/Kg)	3,6	55,2	14,7
Zinc (Zn) (mg/Kg)	0,3	9,6	8,3
Copper (Cu) (mg/kg)	0,6	21	4,8
Manganese (Mn) (mg/kg)	6	132	2,65

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Athalassa Plant Composition season 2024-2025

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Achelia Plant Composition season 2024-2025

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Kivisili Plant Composition season 2024-2025

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Dry Matter production graphs for season 2024-2025

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Protein Tablet Results(% in Dry Matter) for season 2024-2025

Samples	ACHELIA	KIVISILI	ATHALASSA
1) Triticum aestivum	11,44	8,69	8,05
2) Lolium multiflorum	11,83	13,74	6,52
3) T.aestivum/Triticale	11,85	9,75	9,32
4) T.aestivum/L.molitiflorum	7,94	7,46	6,15
5) SUPERFIVE	9,27	10,31	7,07
6) FIENO	10,34	9,83	7,46
7) Vicia sativa	15,11	17,83	8,38
8) Lathyrus ochrus	16,82	NIL	7,37
9) Medicago polymorpha	15,46	10,70	8,97
10) Trifolium michelianum	15,20	NIL	9,23
11) T.aestivum(NEW VARIETY)	7,83	7,95	7,57
12) Triticale(ACHERITU)	6,69	7,03	6,39
13) T.aestivum/L.ochrus	10,67	8,86	9,87
14) T.aestivum/V.sativa	9,64	8,12	8,29

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Ash Tablet Results(% in Dry Matter) for season 2024-2025

Samples	ACHELIA	KIVISILI	ATHALASSA
1) Triticum aestivum	11,15	8,53	6,87
2) Lolium multiflorum	12,20	10,48	7,87
3) T.aestivum/Triticale	11,61	8,64	7,76
4) T.aestivum/L.molitiflorum	10,36	9,19	6,43
5) SUPERFIVE	10,68	7,85	7,87
6) FIENO	10,93	9,67	8,23
7) Vicia sativa	13,55	9,77	8,08
8) Lathyrus ochrus	12,82	NIL	8,13
9) Medicago polymorpha	10,46	11,35	8,06
10) Trifolium michelianum	15,74	NIL	9,35
11) T. aestivum (NEW VARIETY)	9,46	9,53	5,71
12) Triticale (ACHERITU)	8,40	6,44	5,92
13) T.aestivum/L.ochrus	12,25	8,19	8,01
14) T.aestivum/V.sativa	11,24	6,83	7,07

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Dry Matter production graphs for season 2025-2026 (intermediate sampling)

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Dry Matter production graphs for season 2025-2026 (intermediate sampling)

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Dry matter weight for each treatment (after 62 days from sowing) for the first year

Samples	t/ha
1 (Common Wheat)	1,59
2 (Ryegrass)	1,17
3 (Common Wheat/Triticale)	2,19
4 (Common Wheat/Ryegrass)	1,25
5 (Superfive)	1,45
6 (Fieno)	1,55
7(Vetch)	0,83
8(Grass Pea)	0,23
9(Bur clover)	0,51
10(Balansa clover)	0,05
11 (Common wheat new variety)	1,63
12(Triticale)	1,78
13(Common Wheat/ Grass Pea)	0,71
14(Common Wheat/ Vetch)	1,46

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conclusions

- Some forages had serious problem with weeds (clover)
- Some forages did not grow
- The best treatment - forage was *Triticale*
- The second-best treatments were the mixtures of several species
- Final results to be evaluated....

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Leading / Contribution to WP3 – work from other partners

WP N°	3	Lead beneficiary						ECoE			
WP title	Enhanced productivity, adaptiveness and diversification of crops, pastures, forages										
Participant N°	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
Short name	IPB	ECoE	APRI	SELMET	MoSAR	UNISS	IAV	UIZ	CTC	ITACyL	IRA
PM/participant	15.65	8	9	4.9	2.2	8	10	11.4	1	3	11
Start month	3					End month			30		

The are three main pillars or targets of this WP :

- Strategies to enhanced productivity, adaptiveness and diversification of crops, pastures, forages (if anyone works with that please fw to me)
- The use of Agro-byproducts as animal feeds – (if anyone works with that please fw to me)
- To develop predictive models for pastures, forages and crop productivities (if anyone works with that please fw to me)

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Deliverables of WP3

- D3.1: Formulas for **feed blocks with byproducts** (R, PU; Month 18)
- D3.2: Efficacy of the intervention strategies on **crop** productivity and quality (R, PU; Month 26)
- D3.3; Efficacy of the intervention strategies on **pastures** productivity and quality (R, PU; Month 26)
- D3.4: Efficacy of the intervention strategies on **forage** productivity and quality (R, PU; Month 26)
- D3.5: **Predictive models** for pastures, forages and crop productivities (R, PU; Month 30)

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WP N°	4		Lead beneficiary				APRI				
WP title	Enhanced productivity of local breeds										
Participant N°	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
Short name	IPB	ECoE	APRI	SELMET	MoSAR	UNISS	IAV	UIZ	CTC	ITACyL	IRA
PM/participant	14.5	10	12	4.9	9	14	10	10.8	4	6	6
Start month	3				End month			30			

Deliverables

- D4.1: General strategies to be tested to improve livestock productivity performance (R, PU; Month 6)
- D4.2: Benchmarked productivity of non-intervened livestock from living labs (R, CO; Month 10)
- D4.3: Report on animal health and welfare in the participating living labs (R, PU; Month 24)
- D4.4: Efficacy of the intervention strategies on animal productivity and carcass quality (R, PU; Month 29)
- D4.5: Predictive models for enhanced management of local breeds (R, PU; Month 30)

Task 4.3. Strategies towards enhanced productivity and management of meat/dairy livestock (M4-M24)
 (Lead: APRI; Participants: IPB, ECoE, SELMET, MoSAR, UNISS, IAV, UIZ, ITACyL, CTC, IRA)

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Mushroom consumption

There are approximately 12,000 species of mushrooms

Global production
2018 → 13.000.000 tn

2026 → 21.000.000 tn !!!!!!!!!!!!!!!

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Properties of mushrooms

Antioxidant
(Liu et al., 2015)

Antifungal
(Kang et al., 2017)

Anti-bacterial
(Zhu, et al., 2012)

Anti-aging
(Zhang et al., 2016)

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Objective of the study

Effects of Dietary Supplementation with Oyster Mushroom By-products on Lamb Performance, Meat Quality, Antioxidant capacity and the fatty acid (FA) profile

The influence of dietary supplementation with oyster mushroom waste on lamb performance (body weight, hot carcass, cold carcass, liver, lungs, heart, spleen, kidneys) and meat quality : Ph, colour (L=lightness, a=redness, b=yellowness), cook loss (%), shear force (N/cm²)

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Materials and Methods- Animals and Groups

Group 0% : receiving a basal diet

a diet supplemented with dried oyster mushroom waste (OMW) of the *Pleurotus ostreatus* species at a rate of:

2% - Group P2

4% - Group P4

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Experimentation diets Preparation of animal feed

	0% Mushroom	2% Mushroom	4% Mushroom
Maize	44	44	44
Barley	13.5	13.5	13.5
Wheat bran	10	9	8
Sunflower oil 28%	8	7	6
Soyabean meal 46%	14	14,5	15
Sugar beet pulp	6	5.5	5
Marble dust - lime	1	1	1
Sodium bicarbonate	0.5	0.5	0.5
Ammonium chloride	0.5	0.5	0.5
Premix	2.5	2.5	2.5
Mushroom	0	2	4
Ufv uni	0.911	0.912	0.913
Crude protein	16.48	16.47	16.46
Crude Fiber	6.03	5.8	5.58
Sugars	40.07	40.51	40.95
Fat	2.62	2.61	2.6
Ash	6.67	6.69	6.71

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Table1. Chemical composition of oyster mushroom (*Pleurotus ostreatus*) waste (OMW) (g/100 g)

OMW*	
Crude protein	12.6
Crude fiber	10.2
Ether extract	2.09
Ash	7.61
Sugars	40.4

*Oyster mushroom (*Pleurotus ostreatus*) waste (OMW)(g/100g)

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Animals and Groups

- ▶ Three-month lambs with similar body weight, which were randomly selected from the flock and used in the present study
- ▶ 24 male Chios lambs were assigned into 3 groups (~30 m² per group indoors)
- ▶ Free access to the outdoors (~90 m² per group)
- ▶ Water ad libitum
- ▶ Twice a day, feeding concentrates at 7 a.m. and at 16 p.m.
- ▶ forage (alfalfa hay) ad libitum

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Growth parameters

- ✓ Body weight
- ✓ Feed intake
- ✓ Hot and Cold carcass weight
- ✓ Internal organ weights

Meat quality measurements

On the 28th day of the experiment, lambs were slaughtered and meat samples were collected for determination of:

- **Meat Quality parameters**
- **Intramuscular Fat**
- **Oxidative Stability**

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Meat quality measurements-pH and Color

A portable **pH meter** (HI 99163 model, Hanna Instruments, Cluj, Romania) was used by inserting the electrode into the **longissimus dorsi muscle** 24 h after slaughter

The standardization of the pH meter

- was carried out with buffers at pH 4.0 and 7.0 (Merck—Darmstadt, Germany)
- at ambient temperature

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Meat quality measurements-Color

The **part of the longissimus dorsi muscle** between the **12th and 13th ribs** was sliced across the fibers

- left exposed to the air at room temperature for blooming for 30 min
- meat color was assessed in triplicate using a Miniscan XE (HunterLab, Reston, VA, USA) chromameter set on the **L*, a*, b*** system (CIE 1976, Commission International de l' Eclairage)
- A white and a black tile were used for the calibration of the chromameter

***L=lightness, *a=redness, *b=yellowness**

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Meat quality measurements- Water Holding Capacity

- ▶ A sample (80 ± 2 g) of the **longissimus thoracis muscle** from each lamb
 - ▶ was weighed
 - ▶ placed in a plastic bag
 - ▶ and cooked in a water bath at 75°C for 35 min
- ▶ Left under tap water for 15 min
- ▶ Then left at room temperature
- ▶ The sample was weighed again
 - ▶ Cooking loss (%)

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Meat quality measurements- Shear Force Value

Three sub samples with a cross section of 1 cm^2 were then cut parallel to the muscle fibers

The shear force value of the *longissimus thoracis* muscle

was measured using a Warner Bratzler (WB) shear blade

fitted to a Zwick Testing Machine Model Z2.5/TN1S (Zwick GmbH and Co, Ulm, Germany)

- Peak force values in Newtons were recorded

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Meat quality measurements -Intramuscular fat

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Measurement of Lipid Oxidation—MDA Assay

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Results

Table 1. Effect of dietary oyster mushroom (*Pleurotus ostreatus*) waste on lamb performance, carcass and internal organ weights.

Parameter	Treatment			SEM	P-value
	C	P2	P4		
BW, g	29.9	30.1	30.4	2.02	0.1250
Hot_Carcass, g	14.9	15.9	16.4	1.07	0.5893
Cold_Carcass, g	14.4	15.3	15.7	1.05	0.6445
Liver, g	0.53	0.53	0.53	0.03	0.9971
Liver, %	2.01	2.02	2.02	0.11	0.9971
Lungs, g	0.47	0.50	0.43	0.03	0.2967
Lungs, %	1.79	1.88	1.63	0.12	0.2967
Heart, g	0.15	0.16	0.14	0.01	0.3101
Heart, %	0.56	0.60	0.54	0.03	0.3101
Spleen, g	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.005	0.8925
Spleen, %	0.21	0.21	0.22	0.02	0.8925
Kidneys, g	0.10	0.11	0.11	0.01	0.7036
Kidneys, %	0.38	0.35	0.40	0.04	0.6195

C= control, P2=2g per100 of feed, P4=4gper100g of feed. BW= body weight, FI= feed intake, %= percentage of BW.

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Results

Table 2. Effect of dietary supplementation with oyster mushroom (*Pleurotus ostreatus*) waste on weekly **body weight** gain of Chios lambs (n=8)

Body weight (kg), days	Treatment			SEM	P-value
	C	2%	4%		
1	27.6	27.6	27.8	2.11	0.9988
7	27.4	27.3	27.6	2.01	0.9911
15	30.6	30.5	31.0	2.04	0.9838
22	31.5	31.9	32.1	1.97	0.9790
29	32.1	33.2	33.6	2.05	0.8683

Table 3. Effect of dietary supplementation with oyster mushroom (*Pleurotus ostreatus*) waste on weekly **feed intake** of Chios lambs (n=8)

Feed intake (kg), Days	Treatment			SEM	P-value
	C	2%	4%		
1	0.55	0.55	0.56	0.04	0.9988
7	0.55	0.55	0.55	0.04	0.9911
15	0.61	0.61	0.62	0.04	0.9838
22	0.63	0.64	0.64	0.04	0.9790
29	0.64	0.66	0.67	0.04	0.8683

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Results

Table 4. Effect of dietary supplementation with oyster mushroom (*Pleurotus ostreatus*) waste on **lamb meat quality** (n=8).

Parameter	Treatment			SEM	P-value
	C	P2	P4		
pH ₂₄	5.75	5.76	5.74	0.03	0.8508
L*	40.4	39.9	37.5	1.01	0.1173
a*	12.8	13.0	14.1	0.50	0.1619
b*	15.2	14.8	15.1	0.50	0.8613
Cooking loss, %	15.4	15.8	15.1	1.25	0.9343
Shear force, N/cm ²	18.9	18.8	18.56	2.18	0.9922
Intramuscular fat, %	2.10	2.49	2.1	0.27	0.5004

C= control, P2=2g per100 of feed, P4=4gper100g of feed. *L=lightness, *a=redness, *b=yellowness system

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Results

►Table 5. The effect of dietary supplementation with oyster mushroom (*Pleurotus ostreatus*) waste , on **oxidative stability of lamb meat** during storage at 4°C (ng of malondialdehyde/g of meat, n=8)

Storage time, days	Treatment			SEM	P-value
	C	P2	P4		
1	39.9	36.9	39.8	5.64	0.9133
3	395.1 ^a	340.8 ^b	339.9 ^b	13.1	0.0100
6	458.2 ^a	410.2 ^b	411.1 ^b	10.6	0.0055
9	648.4	589.3	575.2	33.0	0.2720

C= control, P2=2g per 100 of feed, P4=4gper100g of feed.

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Discussion

The supplementation of lambs' diet with oyster mushroom (*Pleurotus ostreatus*) waste (OMW) **did not affect lamb performance, carcass traits and internal organ.**

No significant differences were observed in meat quality characteristics, such as **pH, color, water holding capacity, shear force values and intramuscular fat** ($P > 0.05$).

Oxidative stability was ameliorated, possibly due to antioxidant properties of OMW, which had a positive effect on meat oxidative stability (at 4°C), without any adverse effects on performance or meat quality.

These findings indicate that this byproduct may be successfully employed in lambs' diets within a circular economy scheme, offering benefits not only to consumers and farmers but also to the environment.

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Effects of Dietary Supplementation with Oyster Mushroom By-products on milk yield, composition, fatty acid profile, oxidation stability and udder health in dairy ewes

Objective of the study

The aim of the present study was to investigate the influence of dietary supplementation with oyster mushroom waste on milk production, composition, oxidative stability and udder health in dairy ewes during the mid stage of lactation (100 ± 5 days after parturition).

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Material and Methods (1) – Animals and Groups

- 16 Chios dairy ewes → 2nd parity and same stage of lactation ~ 100 days after parturition)
- Assigned to 2 groups → Control (**C**) that was fed with a basal concentrate diet, and a **P4** group that was offered the same diet supplemented with dried oyster mushroom waste (OMW) from *Pleurotus ostreatus* at 4 %.
- The duration of the experiment was 4 weeks.
- Commercial OMW deriving from *Pleurotus ostreatus* industrial-scale cultivation (Manitus S.A., Athens, Greece)

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Material and Methods (2) – Animals and Groups

- Each ewe group was housed in an individual pen, which was divided into an outdoor and indoor area and had the same covered area (3 m²/ewe), similar orientation, and was equipped with 8 individual troughs for feeding.
- At the beginning of the experiment, all animals were provided with a basal concentrate diet for a week, serving as an adaptation period.

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Ingredients (%)	Control	P4
Corn	58.70	55.10
Sunflower Meal	10.00	10.00
Soyabean meal 45% OMW	23.80 -	23.40 4.00
Limestone	1.30	1.30
Monocalcium Phosphate	0.80	0.80
Sodium Chloride (NaCl)	0.60	0.60
Molasses	2.00	2.00
Bentonite	0.30	0.30
Vitamins and Trace elements Premix	2.50	2.50
Analysis (%)		
Dry Matter	88.97	88.96
Ash	8.49	8.67
Crude protein	17.50	17.50
Fat	2.71	2.65
Crude Fiber	5.47	5.72
Ca	1.30	1.30
P	0.65	0.65
Mg	0.25	0.25
Na	0.46	0.45
NE (MJ)	7.20	7.10

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Milk Yield and Composition

- Milking of ewes was carried out twice daily, at 6:00 a.m. and 18:00 p.m., in a 12-stall milking parlor (Westfalia, Radar-Wiedenbrück, Germany).
- Milk yield, calculated as the total quantity of the collected milk during the morning and afternoon, was determined on day 1 prior to, and on days 7, 14, 21 and 28 after, OMW addition.
- Collection of individual milk samples in tubes appropriately labeled were also carried out on acclimation week and at weeks 1–4 after OMW dietary supplementation for the direct assessment of lactose, protein, fat and total solids-not-fat content, while pH and somatic cell count was also measured by using the Lactoscan COMBO Milk Cell Analyser (Lactosan, Nova Zagora, Bulgaria).

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Material and Methods (4) – Assessed parameters during milking

- Milk oxidative stability was determined by measuring MDA concentration (ng/mL) (on day 1 prior to, and on days 7, 14, 21 and 28 after, OMW addition)
- Milk fatty acids composition was determined by direct methylation of lyophilized samples (day 28)
- Milk samples were also collected (day 28) for isolation of milk somatic cells and classification to polymorphonuclear granulocytes (P), monocytes/macrophages (M) and lymphocytes (L)

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Results

Table 1. Effect of dietary oyster mushroom waste (*Pleurotus ostreatus*) on ewes' milk yield, fat, and protein content.

Parameter	Sampling Day	CONTROL	P4	SEM	P-value
Milk yield (mL/kg)	7	1406	1340	198	*NS
	14	1463	1500	200	NS
	21	1469	1444	176	NS
	28	1450	1388	187	NS
Fat (%)	7	4,54	4,57	0,29	NS
	14	4,12	4,56	0,31	NS
	21	3,98	4,40	0,34	NS
	28	5,37	3,87	0,6	NS
Protein (%)	7	4,56	4,57	0,06	NS
	14	4,62	4,56	0,05	NS
	21	4,65	4,62	0,06	NS
	28	4,56	4,73	0,11	NS

*NS= Not significant.

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Results

Table 2. Effect of dietary oyster mushroom waste (*Pleurotus ostreatus*) on ewes' milk **total solids-not-fat (%)**, lactose, and pH.

Parameter	Sampling Day	CONTROL	P4	SEM	P-value
Total solids-not-fat (%)	7	9,60	9,64	0,13	*NS
	14	9,74	9,62	0,11	NS
	21	9,80	9,74	0,13	NS
	28	9,60	9,99	0,25	NS
Lactose (%)	7	4,31	4,33	0,06	NS
	14	4,38	4,32	0,05	NS
	21	4,40	4,37	0,06	NS
	28	4,32	4,49	0,11	NS
pH	7	6,57	6,6	0,06	NS
	14	6,56	6,56	0,05	NS
	21	6,54	6,57	0,06	NS
	28	6,55	6,55	0,11	NS

*NS= Not significant.

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Results

Table 3. Effect of dietary oyster mushroom waste (*Pleurotus ostreatus*) on ewes' milk somatic cell count (SCC).

	Sampling Day	Control	P4	SEM	p-value
SCC	7	59911	84537	21733	*NS
	14	41796	38935	21273	NS
	21	173403	97342	51328	NS
	28	127782	74978	62894	NS

*NS= Not significant.

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Results

Table 4. Effect of dietary oyster mushroom waste (*Pleurotus ostreatus*) on ewes' milk MDA (Malondialdehyde).

	Sampling Day	Control	P4	SEM	p-value
MDA (ng/kg)	7	8,98	7,61	1,07	<0,1
	14	9,43	7,53	1,27	<0,05
	21	4,72	4,32	0,56	NS
	28	5,35	4,91	0,52	NS

*NS= Not significant.

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Results

Table 5. Effect of dietary oyster mushroom waste (*Pleurotus ostreatus*) on the immune cell profile of ewes' milk

Parameter	Control	P4	SEM	p-value
Lymphocyte (L) (%)	0,65	0,53	0,08	*NS
Macrophage (M) (%)	0,04	0,03	0,02	NS
Polymorphonuclear leucocytes (P) (%)	0,31	0,36	0,07	NS
L/(M + P)	2,91	2,04	0,70	NS

*NS= Not significant.

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Table 6. Effect of dietary oyster mushroom waste (*Pleurotus ostreatus*) on the immune cell profile of ewes' milk (1)

Fatty acid, g/100g fat	Control	P4	SEM	p-value
C4:0	1,36	1,26	0,07	0.329
C6:0	1,74	1,63	0,08	0.314
C8:0	2,34	2,21	0,08	0.273
C10:0	9,57	8,76	0,30	0.080
C11:0	0,30	0,32	0,02	0.307
C12:0	5,66	5,08	0,25	0.120
C14:0	13,46	13,1	0,36	0.476
C14:1	0,62	0,62	0,01	0.726
C15:0	0,97	0,98	0,07	0.949
C15:1	0,23	0,23	0,02	0.570
C16:0	32,6	33,8	0,90	0.384
C16:1	0,80	0,82	0,10	0.881

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Table 6. Effect of dietary oyster mushroom waste (*Pleurotus ostreatus*) on the immune cell profile of ewes' milk (2)

Fatty acid,g/100 g fat			SEM	p-value
	Control	P4		
C17:0	0,46	0,57	0,12	0.551
C17:1	0,48	0,59	0,07	0.260
C18:0	6,66	6,19	0,36	0.373
C18:1cis9	15,9	17,0	0,78	0.338
C18:2cis6	2,57	2,63	0,13	0.753
C18:3n3	0,17	0,15	0,03	0.611
SFA	75,2	73,9	0,94	0.356
PUFA	3,68	3,75	0,16	0.776
MUFA	18,0	19,2	0,76	0.279

91

Discussion

- ❖ Dietary supplementation with oyster mushroom by-products improved milk oxidative stability, without negatively affecting **milk yield** or composition in ewes.
- ❖ MDA levels were lower in group P4, suggesting enhanced oxidative stability in the milk of animals supplemented with OMW.
- ❖ No significant effects were detected in milk SCC and somatic cell subset percentages.

92

Conclusion

- ❖ OMW appears as a potential unconventional feedstuff in the diets of dairy ewes in the context of sustainability, circular economy and protection of natural resources.
- ❖ Dietary supplementation with oyster mushroom by-products improves milk oxidative stability, without negatively affecting milk yield, composition, or the health status of ewes during at mid-lactation (100 ± 5 days after parturition).
- ❖ Further experimentation is warranted.

93

Project on weaning method in small ruminants

There are three main management systems in Cyprus

traditional

- Lambs suckling their dams for 4 to 6 weeks
- Ewes are not milked

modern

- Lambs or kids are weaned after birth and reared artificially for the first 4 to 6 weeks
- Ewes machined milked twice per day

Which is the best regarding quality of marketable milk ?

in between, partial suckling

- Lambs or kids partial suckle their dams some hours per day for the first 4-6 weeks
- Ewes or goats are machined milked once daily

94

Objective

The objective of the present work was to investigate the effect of continuous suckling of kids on composition of surplus commercial milk of their dams during the pre-weaning period of Damascus goat, the most common goat breed of Cyprus.

Investigation of the effect of simultaneous suckling/milking:

- On milk production,
- quality characteristics of marketable milk,
- and gene expression in the mammary epithelium.

In Damascus goats

95

Experimental design

❖ No suckling group: NK

❖ Mixed rearing group: SK (suckling and milking)

- ✓ Kid Suckling: 7 weeks (until weanig)
- ✓ Observation period: 31 weeks (milk yield and content measured weekly for 10 weeks then monthly)

Group	N	Machine milking	Kid Suckling
NK	15	2	NO
SK	15	2	YES

Goat groups balanced for:

- ✓ Weight and nutritional status
- ✓ Nutrition: mixed ration (TMR) of roughage and concentrated feed *ad libitum*
- ✓ **Lactation period: 1st**
- ✓ Number of fetuses carried: 1.4 per goat
- ✓ All animals were healthy throughout the experimental period.

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Measurements - Analyses - Sampling:

- Weekly milk production measurements
- Weekly milk composition analyses (LactoStar 3510) and fatty acid profile (GCMS-QP2010 Plus)
- Mammary gland sampling at weaning
 - 49 days post-partum (biopsy collection)
 - 6 animals per group

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Effect of mixed rearing on Milk Composition

Protein content: No statistically significant differences were found.

Increase in fat content in the SK handling group during the weeks leading up to weaning.

98

Effect of mixed rearing on Commercial Milk

Daily Milk Production in the SK group compared to the NK group:

- ✓ Lower until weaning
- ✓ No difference after weaning - week 9 to 31

99

- ❖ The **commercial milk** produced until weaning (up to week 7) was lower for the suckling/milking group compared to the two-milking group
- ❖ The **commercial milk** produced cumulatively after weaning (week 7 to week 31) was higher for the suckling/milking group compared to the two-milking group
- ❖ Overall, the suckling/milking group had no significant difference in milk production compared to the two mechanical milking group.
- ❖ The fat and protein content was not affected
- ❖ The work on gene expression is undergoing

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Dissemination and communication

- For our past and accepted conference participations, we started with the 8th Animal Science Congress in Thessaloniki 2025. The titled was: The effect of Mushroom By-products on the Oxidation Stability and Quality Characteristics.
- 3rd Pancyprian Conference "Rural Development: From Research to Practice" on May 8-9, 2025, in Lefkara, Cyprus. entitled Incorporation of discarded Pleurotus ostreatus mushroom stems into lamb diets " and was authored
- At the 76th EAAP Annual Meeting in Innsbruck, Austria (August 25-29, 2025),: Effects of Dietary Supplementation with Oyster Mushroom By-products on Lamb Performance and Meat Quality, and
- At the 76th EAAP Annual Meeting in Innsbruck, Austria (August 25-29, 2025),: The influence of dietary supplementation with oyster mushroom waste on antioxidant capacity and the fatty acid (FA) profile of the lamb's meat.
- Additionally, at the 39o Annual Scientific Conference of the Hellenic Zootechnical Society (E.Z.E.) in Ioannina (October 15-17, 2025), we have an presentation titled: THE USE OF DISPOSED MUSHROOM CULTURE STRAINS Pleurotus ostreatus in dairy sheep,
- For our upcoming conference submissions, 77th EAAP Annual Meeting in Hamburg, Germany (September 7-11, 2026). The title: Effects of dietary supplementation with oyster mushroom by-products on milk yield, composition, oxidation stability and udder health in dairy ewes, authored.
- Finally, regarding the articles to be submitted to distinguished journals, we have prepared two manuscripts. The first article is titled: Effects of Dietary Supplementation with Oyster Mushroom By-products on Lamb Performance, Meat Quality, Antioxidant capacity and the fatty acid (FA) profile, by A. The second article is titled: Effects of Dietary Supplementation with Oyster Mushroom By-products on milk yield, composition, fatty acid profile, oxidation stability and udder health in dairy ewes,

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Τμήμα Γεωπονικών Επιστημών,
Βιοτεχνολογίας και Επιστήμης Τροφίμων

Τεχνολογικό Πανεπιστήμιο Κύπρου

Έρευνα στη Βιολογική Κτηνοτροφία: Εθνικά και Διεθνή Προγράμματα

Παρουσίαση των προγραμμάτων OrganicDairy και PAS-AGRO-PAS

Ομότιμος Τμηματικός Αναπληρωτής Καθηγητής

Έρευνα για την ποιότητα των γαλακτοκομικών προϊόντων

Τα σημαντικά ευρήματα της έρευνας "βελτίωση των λιπιδίων στο πρόβριο γάλα και το χαλόνισμα προς πιο υγιεινά, τοπικά προϊόντα" παρουσιάσθησαν το τμήμα Γεωπονικών Επιστημών, Βιοτεχνολογίας και Επιστήμης Τροφίμων (ΓΕΒΕΤ) του **Τεχνολογικού Πανεπιστημίου** Κύπρου (ΤΕΠΑΚ). Η παρουσίαση των αποτελεσμάτων του διετούς ερευνητικού Προγράμματος που χρηματοδοτήθηκε από την Κομνηνή Δημοκρατία και τα θεσμοθετικά τμήματα της Ευρωπαϊκής Ένωσης έγινε στο πλαίσιο ημερίδας στο **ΤΕΠΑΚ**.

Κατά τη διάρκεια της μέρας, παρά ερευνητικές μεθόδους προσδιορίσθησαν και επισημάνθησαν η ποιότητα του λιπιδίου του γάλακτος αναπτύχθηκαν με την συνεργασία του **ΤΕΠΑΚ**, του **Πανεπιστημίου** Ιωαννίνων και του Πολυτεχνείου Κρήτης, ενώ ερευνητές και από τα τρία ιδρύματα παρουσίασαν αποτελεσμάτα των νέων τεχνικών σε ευρύ κοινό. Παρουσιάστηκαν επίσης αποτελέσματα και Επιστήμης Τροφίμων (**ΤΕΠΙΛΑΚ**), και κώ-

ΧΑΡΑ ΛΑΜΠΙΔΑΚΗ ΚΡΗΤΗΣ, Γενικό Γραμματέας ΤΕΠΑΚ

1 **Running head: Kid suckling: goat milk & udder transcriptome**

2

3 **Interpretive Summary**

4 Allowing does to nurture their kids is considered advantageous for animal welfare and farm

5 management. Here we investigated the effect of Damascus kids suckling, as compared to

6 artificial rearing, on milk production traits and mammary gland gene expression. Rearing

7 method affected milk production only pre-weaning, while milk protein and fat content was

8 unaffected. Fatty acid profile under mixed rearing was more favorable for human health.

9 Furthermore, we identified genes involved in mammary gland regeneration, healing and

10 nutrient transport that were affected by the rearing method applied. Overall, kid-suckling did

11 not compromise milk production traits while it improved milk nutritional value.

12

13 **Kid Suckling vs Artificial Rearing: effects in goat milk parameters and the mammary**

14 **gland transcriptome**

15 Eleni Stakianaki¹, Despoina Miliadou², Konstantina Konstantinou², Simoni Symeou²,

16 Georgios C. Stefanos¹, Ariadne L. Hager-Theodorides^{1*} and Ouranios Tzamaloukas^{2†}

Ποιότητα των βιολογικών γαλακτοκομικών προϊόντων στην Κύπρο

Αποτελέσματα σχετικά με το προφίλ του λίπους του γάλακτος που είναι διαθέσιμο στην λιανική

40% αύξηση

40% αύξηση

42% αύξηση

ANOVA P-values ***: P<0.001, **: P<0.01, *: P<0.05, P=0.05

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D 7.1. Centralized Database for Cultivation Results: Development, Analysis, and Recommendations

Summary

This deliverable outlines the development of a centralized database to organize, store, and analyze cultivation data collected in Cyprus during 2022 and 2023. The database aims to facilitate data sharing and comparison among partners, to promote collaborative insights and support sustainable agricultural practices. The below data concern yield trends by province and crop type.

Background

The agricultural sector in Cyprus faces significant challenges, including limited arable land and climate-related pressures. To address these, the program focuses on improving data-driven decision-making through a centralized database. This database serves as a foundational tool for future agricultural initiatives.

Methodology

Data Collection

Cultivation data for 2022 and 2023 were collected from all provinces of Cyprus: Nicosia, Limassol, Larnaca, Paphos and Famagusta. Data were categorized by crop-type and location.

Results

FALLOW

• 2022 • 2023

CULTIVATIONS

814656,9 810127,9

• 2022 • 2023

The data reveals differences in cultivation trends across the four provinces of Cyprus between 2022 and 2023. Below is a summary of the total cultivation areas and fallow areas by year:

- Total Cultivations:**
 - 2022: 831,646.6 (52%)

D 5.1

Quality and Safety of Agro-pastoral Products from Living Labs Pre-intervention

1. Introduction

The Making of Fragile Agro-ecosystems Productive, Adaptive, and Sustainable: Multifunctional Agro-pastoralism project aims to enhance the resilience and sustainability of agro-pastoral systems. A key aspect of this project involves evaluating the quality and safety of agro-pastoral products from living labs before implementing any intervention measures. This deliverable focuses on presenting the quality of milk ie fatty acid (FA) profile of milk produced under conventional farming system applied in Cyprus which characterized by low grazing forage participation in the diets (use of forage between 40 to 50% as the percentage of the total diet) in small ruminants. By analyzing the FA profiles, we aim to establish a baseline of the milk lipids produced, providing as well insights on the existing literature for potential improvements in product quality using agro-pastoral practices (high grazing or forage use).

2. Background

2.1. Agro-pastoral Systems

Agro-pastoral systems integrate agricultural and livestock production, playing a crucial role in rural livelihoods and sustainable land management. These systems are especially important in fragile ecosystems, where they enhance resilience to environmental stresses and contribute to food security. In those systems the feeding is based more on forages either as grazing or fed roughage material. By combining crop cultivation and animal husbandry, agro-pastoral systems optimize resource use, and improve possibly the quality of the products produced under agro-pastoral methods of animal husbandry respecting the feeding ethology.

2.2. Forage: Concentrate ratio in ruminant diets

As has been suggested by several researchers, the milk's FA profile is affected by the forage participation in the animal diets and FA is a key determinant of the nutritional quality and health benefits of the animal products. The FA present in milk can impact the end product (cheese, yogurt) and consequently various human health outcomes, such as cardiovascular health, inflammatory responses, and metabolic processes. Higher forage participation in the feed, such as those applied in organic farming or grass-fed systems may lead to different

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Thanks for you attention

The study was funded by the PAS-AGRO-PAS program within the framework of the PRIMA action

The PRIMA programme is supported and funded under Horizon 2020, the Framework European Union's Programme for Research and Innovation

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PAS - AGRO - PAS

The Making of Fragile Agro-ecosystems Productive, Adaptive and Sustainable: Multifunctional Agro-pastoralism

Arid Land Institute (IRA), Medenine (Tunisia), 12-13 may 2026

ITACyL (Spain) update

Raúl Bodas

Partner identification

- ITACyL. Agrarian Technological Institute of Castille and León (Spain). Contact person & PI: Raúl Bodas

Main WP and tasks:

- WP2. Strategies towards enhanced productivity, adaptiveness and diversification of crops
 - Task 2.1: Conceptual modelling; Task 2.2: Data collection; Task 2.3. Assessment of agro-pastoral systems' health
- WP3. Enhanced productivity, adaptiveness and diversification of crops, pastures, forages
 - Task 3.1, 3.2 & 3.3. Strategies towards enhanced crops, forages, pastures; Task 3.4: Agro-byproducts as animal feed; Task 3.5: Predictive models
- WP4. Enhanced productivity of local breeds
 - Task 4.1. Benchmarking of productivity of livestock; Task 4.2. Animal growth; Task 4.3. Strategies enhanced productivity; Task 4.4. Animal health and welfare; Task 4.5. Biometry, sensing and animal activity
- WP5. Valorisation of agro-pastoral food products
 - Task 5.1: Multi-dimensional quality; Task 5.2: Typicity and differentiation; Task 5.3: Innovative agro-pastoral food products; Task 5.4: Shelf-life
- WP6. Enhanced economic and social conditions for agro-pastoralism livelihoods
- WP7. Multi-functional sustainable agro-pastoralism in the Agriculture 4.0 era
- WP8. Training, communication and dissemination

Main deliverables:

Nº	Deliverable name	WP	Leader	Type	Level	Due
D2.3	Agro-ecosystem health assessments of the systems	2	IPB	R	PU	M10
D2.4	Transversal analysis of farms characterisation	2	SELMET	R	PU	M15
D3.2	Efficacy of strategies on crop productivity/quality	3	ECOE	R	PU	M26
D3.4	Efficacy of strategies on forage productivity/quality	3	IAV	R	PU	M26
D3.5	Predictive models for pastures, forage and crops	3	ECOE	R	PU	M30
D4.1	Strategies to be tested to improve livestock product	4	APRI	R	PU	M6
D4.3	Animal health and welfare in the living labs	4	ITACyL	R	PU	M24
D4.4	Efficacy of strategies on animal productivity	4	APRI	R	PU	M29
D4.5	Predictive models for enhanced management	4	SELMET	R	PU	M30
D5.1	Quality/safety of agropastoral foods pre-intervention	5	CTC	R	PU	M14
D5.3	Quality of newly developed functional foods	5	CTC	R	PU	M26
D5.4	Shelf-life models of agro-pastoral foods	5	IPB	DEM	PU	M30
D5.5	Quality/safety agro-pastoral foods post-intervention	5	CTC	R	PU	M31
D5.6	Notebooks of quality requisites for labelling	5	SELMET	R	PU	M32
D6.1	Pricing and profitability of agro-pastoral foods	6	UNISS	R	CO	M22
D6.2	Comparative evaluation and SWOT analysis	6	UNISS	R	PU	M26
D6.3	Guidelines and strategic plan to improve policies	6	UNISS	R	PU	M30
D7.1	Centralised database for data acquisition/storage	7	IPB	Other	PU	M12
D8.1	Communication plan	8	UIZ	R	PU	M3
D8.2	Draft of the Data management plant	8	IPB	R	CO	M5
D8.3	First divulgation materials	8	IRA	DEC	PU	M6
D8.4	First version of the PAS-AGRO-PAS website	8	UIZ	DEC	PU	M7
D8.5	Intermediate PEDR	8	IPB	DEM	CO	M18
D8.6	Final Data management plan	8	IPB	R	CO	M28
D8.7	Final PEDR	8	IPB	DEM	CO	M35
D8.8	The PAS-AGRO-PAS Final Seminar	8	UIZ	DEM	PU	M36

- Main WP and tasks:

- WP2. Strategies towards enhanced productivity, adaptiveness and diversification of crops

- Task 2.1: Conceptual modelling; Task 2.2: Data collection; Task 2.3. Assessment of agro-pastoral systems' health

- Data from 1 organic, extensive, meat, dairy and cheese sheep farm. 2023 & 2024. Not sent.

- Working on biodiversity, soil conservation and climate change mitigation in 3 plots

- WP3. Enhanced productivity, adaptiveness and diversification of crops, pastures, forages

- Task 3.1, 3.2 & 3.3. Strategies towards enhanced crops, forages, pastures; Task 3.4: Agro-byproducts as animal feed; Task 3.5: Predictive models

- Cereal and legume mix plots for forage, pasture and grain. Still to finish lab and data analysis.

- Tried to interchange seeds with Cyprus but not possible.

- WP4. Enhanced productivity of local breeds

- Task 4.1. Benchmarking of productivity of livestock; Task 4.2. Animal growth; Task 4.3. Strategies enhanced productivity; Task 4.4. Animal health and welfare; Task 4.5. Biometry, sensing and animal activity

- Agro-byproducts: grape seed pomace for fattening lambs: Churra (extensive) and Castellana (intensive).

- Animal growth trials (Churra, Castellana): productivity, health, welfare, GPS, wool and saliva cortisol (analysis ongoing).

- WP5. Valorisation of agro-pastoral food products

- Task 5.1: Multi-dimensional quality; Task 5.2: Typicity and differentiation; Task 5.3: Innovative agro-pastoral food products; Task 5.4: Shelf-life

- Collaboration with CTC: *Ovella gallega* cortisol and WP5

- Carcass and meat quality (incl. shelf-life)

- Lamb patties using plant extracts (coord. with CTC). Possible dry cured meat (not sure)

- WP6. Enhanced economic and social conditions for agro-pastoralism livelihoods

- Some economic data from farm could contribute

- WP7. Multi-functional sustainable agro-pastoralism in the Agriculture 4.0 era

- WP8. Training, communication and dissemination

- Participation in meetings and course (Univ. Sassari 2025)

- Main deliverables:

Nº	Deliverable name	WP	Leader	Type	Level	Due
D2.3	Agro-ecosystem health assessments of the systems	2	IPB	R	PU	M10
D2.4	Transversal analysis of farms characterisation	2	SELMET	R	PU	M15
D3.2	Efficacy of strategies on crop productivity/quality	3	ECoE	R	PU	M26
D3.4	Efficacy of strategies on forage productivity/quality	3	IAV	R	PU	M26
D3.5	Predictive models for pastures, forage and crops	3	ECoE	R	PU	M30
D4.1	Strategies to be tested to improve livestock product	4	APRI	R	PU	M6
D4.3	Animal health and welfare in the living labs	4	ITACyL	R	PU	M24
D4.4	Efficacy of strategies on animal productivity	4	APRI	R	PU	M29
D4.5	Predictive models for enhanced management	4	SELMET	R	PU	M30
D5.1	Quality/safety of agropastoral foods pre-intervention	5	CTC	R	PU	M14
D5.3	Quality of newly developed functional foods	5	CTC	R	PU	M26
D5.4	Shelf-life models of agro-pastoral foods	5	IPB	DEM	PU	M30
D5.5	Quality/safety agro-pastoral foods post-intervention	5	CTC	R	PU	M31
D5.6	Notebooks of quality requisites for labelling	5	SELMET	R	PU	M32
D6.1	Pricing and profitability of agro-pastoral foods	6	UNISS	R	CO	M22
D6.2	Comparative evaluation and SWOT analysis	6	UNISS	R	PU	M26
D6.3	Guidelines and strategic plan to improve policies	6	UNISS	R	PU	M30
D7.1	Centralised database for data acquisition/storage	7	IPB	Other	PU	M12
D8.1	Communication plan	8	UIZ	R	PU	M3
D8.2	Draft of the Data management plan	8	IPB	R	CO	M5
D8.3	First divulgation materials	8	IRA	DEC	PU	M6
D8.4	First version of the PAS-AGRO-PAS website	8	UIZ	DEC	PU	M7
D8.5	Intermediate PEDR	8	IPB	DEM	CO	M18
D8.6	Final Data management plan	8	IPB	R	CO	M28
D8.7	Final PEDR	8	IPB	DEM	CO	M35
D8.8	The PAS-AGRO-PAS Final Seminar	8	UIZ	DEM	PU	M36

- Small contribution till now.
- Most of data generated from 2025.
- To be done:
 - Providing data for agronomic, animal and meat (agropastoral productos) databases and predictive models.
 - Possibility of providing data (too late) for farms characterization.
 - Gather data of D4.3 from partners and produce deliverable.

Commun./dissem. activities

- Project presented at the annual conference of the Spanish Society of Sheep and Goats Study (*Sociedad Española de Ovinotecnia y Caprinotecnia, SEOC*) Bilbao (Spain), 1-3 Oct 2025.
- Pérez-Barbería, F.J.; Bodas, R. Environmental and Societal Impacts of Protecting Traditional Pastoralism from Wolf Predation in Spain. *Sustainability* 2025, 17, 8189. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su17188189>
- Cittadini, A.; Bermúdez, R.; Cadavez, V.; González-Peaguda, A.; Bodas, R.; Lorenzo, J.M. Influence of Agro-Industrial By-Products Inclusion on Growth Parameters and Carcass Quality in Ovella Galega Lambs. *Animals* 2026, 16, 921. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ani16060921>
- Grape pomace as ingredient for extensively reared Churra lambs: effect on animal performance and fatty acid content. S. E. Charef, C. Vieira, B. Martínez, J. J. García-García, A. Benito, S. Olmedo, R. Bodas. 4th EAAP Regional Meeting 2026. Sassari, 22-24 May 2026
- Grape pomace for fattening Castellana lambs: preliminary productive results. S.E. Charef, C. Vieira, J.J. García- García, A. Benito, R. Bodas. To be presented in the SEOC Conference, Cádiz (Spain), september 2026.

- Other conference and scientific publications will be elaborated from now onwards
- Part of the data will be included in one on course PhD thesis

- ITACyL [website](#)

- SICAMPO: agronomic fair in Madrid, 2025

Final commitments

- There is no such thing as a responsible person
- To be done:
 - Providing data for agronomic, animal and meat (agropastoral productos) databases and predictive models.
 - Possibility of providing data (too late) for farms characterization.
 - Gather data of D4.3 from partners and produce deliverable.
 - Complete the work on animal, meat and products charact.
 - Supporting partners: CTC
 - Produce one scientific paper
- Deadline: 31 may 2027

THE MAKING OF FRAGILE AGRO-ECOSYSTEMS PRODUCTIVE, ADAPTIVE AND SUSTAINABLE: MULTIFUNCTIONAL AGRO-PASTORALISM

centro tecnolóxico da carne

May 12nd-14st, 2026

3rd Face-to-Face Meeting
Medenine (Tunisia)

IP: José Manuel Lorenzo
jmlorenzo@ceteca.net

Meeting agenda

1

Main WPs update

2

Work towards deliverables and planned work

3

Communication/dissemination activities

4

Final commitments

5

Q&A

Work Packages

WP	Denomination/Month# as per proposal	Leader
1	Management and coordination	IPB
2	Diagnosis of the agro-ecosystem/socio-economic traits of the agro-pastoral production systems	SELMET
3	Enhanced productivity, adaptiveness and diversification of crops, pastures, forages	ECoE
4	Enhanced productivity of local breeds	APRI
5	Valorisation of agro-pastoral food products	CTC
6	Enhanced economic and social conditions for agro-pastoralism livelihoods	IPB
7	Multi-functional sustainable agro-pastoralism in the Agriculture 4.0 era	IPB
8	Training, communication and dissemination	UIZ

Deliverables

Nº	Deliverable name	WP	Leader
D1.1	The PAS-AGRO-PAS Pack of Methods	1	IPB
D1.2	The full PAS-AGRO-PAS Pack of Methods	1	IPB
D2.4	Transversal analysis of farms characterisation	2	SELMET
D3.1	Formulas for feed blocks	3	IAV
D4.1	Strategies to be tested to improve livestock product	4	APRI
D4.4	Efficacy of strategies on animal productivity	4	APRI
D4.5	Predictive models for enhanced management	4	SELMET
D5.1	Quality/safety of agropastoral foods pre-intervention	5	CTC
D5.3	Quality of newly developed functional foods	5	CTC
D5.4	Shelf-life models of agro-pastoral foods	5	IPB
D5.5	Quality/safety agro-pastoral foods post-intervention	5	CTC
D5.6	Notebooks of quality requisites for labelling	5	SELMET
D6.1	Pricing and profitability of agro-pastoral foods	6	UNISS
D6.2	Comparative evaluation and SWOT analysis	6	UNISS
D6.3	Guidelines and strategic plan to improve policies	6	UNISS
D6.4	e-Commerce platform with first products	6	UNISS
D7.2	PAS-AGRO-PAS e-platform half-way developed	7	IPB
D8.1	Communication plan	8	UIZ
D8.2	Draft of the Data management plant	8	IPB
D8.3	First divulgation materials	8	IRA
D8.4	First version of the PAS-AGRO-PAS website	8	UIZ
D8.5	Intermediate PEDR	8	IPB
D8.6	Final Data management plan	8	IPB
D8.7	Final PEDR	8	IPB
D8.8	The PAS-AGRO-PAS Final Seminar	8	UIZ

WP 3. Enhanced productivity, adaptiveness and diversification of crops, pastures, forages

WP Nº	3		Lead beneficiary					ECoE			
WP title	Enhanced productivity, adaptiveness and diversification of crops, pastures, forages										
Short name	IPB	ECoE	APRI	SELMET	MoSAR	UNISS	IAV	UIZ	CTC	ITACyL	IRA
OM/participant	15.65	8	9	4.9	2.2	8	10	11.4	1	3	11
Start month	3				End month				30		

Task 3.4 – Agro-byproducts as animal feed – Lead: IAV

Work carried out:

- Characterization of dried by-products, feeds' preparation, and analysis for lamb trials.

Chemical composition

Parameters	BG	GP	OC
DM (%)	90.40	91.69	92.15
EE (% DM)	5.50	4.73	14.51
Crude protein (% DM)	17.34	16.39	4.36
Ash (% DM)	4.07	9.74	4.46
Crude fiber (% DM)	12.49	24.28	34.37
ADF (% DM)	17.60	31.40	43.44
NDF (% DM)	35.30	34.81	55.00

Minerals:

BG: P > K > Ca

GP: K > P > Ca

OC: K > P > Ca

Antioxidant activity:

Parameters	BG	GP	OC	SEM
TPC (mg GAE/100g)	91.35	213.50	1212.99	177.662
DPPH (µg TE/g)	160.48	2132.92	15179.57	2356.784
ABTS (mg AA/100 g)	62.70	397.05	2071.86	311.182
FRAP (µmol Fe ²⁺ /100g)	224.60	2384.10	15126.75	2325.356
ORAC (mg TE/g)	3.66	7.39	39.44	5.694
IC ₅₀ (mg/mL)	764.83	93.68	14.03	119.404

OC > GP > BG

Fatty acid profile: > Linoleic acid > Linoleic acid > Oleic acid

53 % FA

62 % FA

69 % FA

Lambs' feeds

	CON	BG10	GP10	OC10
Ingredients (g/kg feed)				
Barley	282	235	235	224
Soybean meal (44% CP)	211	199	202	232
Cracked corn	200	194	190	170
Wheat	120	90	90	100
Brewers' grain	–	100	–	–
Grape pomace	–	–	100	–
Olive-cake	–	–	–	100
Soybean hulls	70	70	70	70
Wheat bran	60	60	60	60
Calcium carbonate	17	17	17	17
Beet molasses	16	16	16	16
Soybean oil	15	10	11	2
Salt	6	6	6	6
Mineral-vitamin premix 0.3% ¹	3	3	3	3
Chemical composition				
DM (%)	88.96	88.77	88.99	89.47
EE (% DM)	2.68	3.10	2.82	2.88
CP (% DM)	18.44	19.2	19.76	19.46
Ash (% DM)	5.23	5.35	5.25	5.70
CF (% DM)	5.39	6.35	6.96	6.97
ADF (% DM)	10.09	10.48	12.74	10.77
NDF (% DM)	37.07	31.5	27.29	29.08
Ca (mg/100g)	216.84	247.32	283.01	298.06
P (mg/100g)	329.54	341.5	383.39	287.03

Fatty acid profile:

g/100 g fatty acids	CON	BG10	GP10	OC10	SEM
C16:0	13.8	14.4	13.11	14.28	0.192
C18:0	3.26	3.34	3.59	2.96	0.085
C18:1n-9	19.94	18.61	19.26	30.69	1.879
C18:2n-6	53.91	53.87	54.90	43.99	1.684
C18:3n-3	5.48	6.01	5.46	4.13	0.263
SFA	18.54	19.28	18.27	18.76	0.140
MUFA	21.85	20.61	21.16	32.90	1.922
PUFA	59.6	60.11	60.57	48.34	1.930
n-3	5.53	6.06	5.51	4.19	0.262
n-6	53.99	53.95	54.97	44.06	1.685

Antioxidant activity:

Parameters	CON	BG10	GP10	OC10	SEM
TPC (mg GAE/100g)	136.76	132.08	163.60	147.92	5.476
DPPH (μg TE/g)	669.16	709.99	675.66	1127.20	73.575
ABTS (mg AA/100 g)	136.93	158.73	137.87	398.43	41.750
FRAP (μmol Fe ²⁺ /100g)	659.46	686.84	624.74	907.39	43.383
ORAC (mg TE/g)	4.99	5.84	5.26	6.93	0.289
IC ₅₀ (mg/mL)	353.83	308.53	334.97	180.86	25.759

Balanced diets (isoenergetic and isoproteic)

Ongoing work:

- Characterization of dried by-products, feeds' preparation, and analysis for goat trials.

Chemical composition:

Parameters	Carob	Citrus
DM (%)	91.37	91.38
EE (%DM)	1.88	3.66
Crude protein (%DM)	7.04	12.12
Ash (%DM)	3.07	5.92
Carbohydrates (%DM)	79.38	69.68

Minerals:

Carob: Ca > K > Na
Citrus: Ca > K > P

Fatty acid profile:

g/100 g fatty acids	Carob	Citrus	SEM
C16:0	22.30	25.79	0.780
C18:0	3.65	2.48	0.263
C18:1n-9	43.65	12.24	7.023
C18:2n-6	19.77	39.48	4.407
C18:3n-3	3.30	8.36	1.132
SFA	30.37	33.78	0.763
MUFA	46.19	18.09	6.285
PUFA	23.43	48.13	5.523
n-3	3.30	8.36	1.132
n-6	19.92	39.62	4.405

> Unsaturated FA

Antioxidant activity:

Parameters	Carob	Citrus	SEM
TPC (mg GAE/100g)	282.19	821.92	121.879
DPPH (µg TE/g)	3903.71	2899.27	228.686
ABTS (mg AA/100 g)	699.12	916.97	65.074
FRAP (µmol Fe ⁺² /100g)	4105.54	4788.84	207.132
ORAC (mg TE/g)	9.81	38.87	6.519
IC ₅₀ (mg/mL)	42.90	68.35	5.713

Deliverables

D3.1 - Formulas for feed blocks (R, PU; Month 19) (IAV) Planned submission: **September 2026**

Planned work

Ingredients (g/kg feed)	Carob ⁷	Citrus ⁷
Barley	317	317
Soybean meal (44% CP)	248	248
(USA) Maize/corn	213	213
(Soft) Wheat (10.2% CP)	100	100
Carob pods	70.0	-
Citrus peels	-	70.0
Dicalcium Phosphate Dihydrate	13.4	13.4
Calcium carbonate	13.2	13.2
Cane molasses	12.0	12.0
Soybean oil	7.50	7.50
Marine Sodium Chloride (98%)	4.00	4.00
Mineral-vitamin premix 0.25% ¹	2.50	2.50
Liquid Microstat	0.75	0.75

Goats' feeds final elaboration and characterization

WP 4. Enhanced productivity of local breeds

WP Nº	4	Lead beneficiary						APRI			
WP title	Enhanced productivity of local breeds										
Short name	IPB	ECoE	APRI	SELMET	MoSAR	UNISS	IAV	UIZ	CTC	ITACyL	IRA
OM/participant	14.5	10	12	4.9	9	14	10	10,8	4	6	6
Start month	3			End month				30			

Time plan

Work carried out:

Growth parameters:

- Live weight
- Average daily gain (ADG)
- Subcutaneous fat thickness (SFT)

~12±1 kg

Carcass quality:

- Carcass weight
- Carcass yields
- SEUROP Classification and fatness degree
- Morphometric measures
- pH (24 h post-mortem)
- Commercial cutting

Meat quality (*Longissimus* muscle):

- Physicochemical parameters
- Nutritional composition
- Sensory evaluation

Growth parameters

- No significant effect ($p > 0.05$) on the initial (7.09 ± 1.12 kg) and final body weights (12.82 ± 1.03 kg)

No significant differences in the finishing period (~64 days)

- ADG values did not present significant differences ($p > 0.05$) among treatments ($87.27 - 101.98$ g/days).

The finishing diet had no significant effect on growth parameters, which showed similar values between treatments (no negative impact).

Subcutaneous fat thickness (In vivo)

- The SFT values did **not** report **significant** ($p > 0.05$) differences at the **beginning** (2.08 ± 0.05 mm) and at the **end** (2.62 ± 0.05 mm) of the finishing period among treatments.

- The finishing diet did **not** significantly affect ($p > 0.05$) the fat deposition **pattern** of lambs during the finishing period.
- All groups showed an increase of **approximately 26%** compared to the initial value.

Carcass characterization

Parameters	CON	BG10	GP10	OC10	SEM	Sig.
HCW (kg)	6.20	6.23	6.43	6.50	0.109	ns
CCW (kg)	5.95	5.90	6.15	6.20	0.098	ns
HCY (%)	48.91	49.82	49.55	49.34	0.394	ns
CCY (%)	46.93	47.25	47.47	47.07	0.351	ns
Conformation ¹	5.25	5.50	6.13	5.75	0.139	ns
Fatness degree ²	5.13	4.63	4.63	4.75	0.125	ns
ECL (cm)	44.38	43.79	43.88	44.71	0.311	ns
ICL (cm)	42.89	43.14	42.25	43.79	0.397	ns
LL (cm)	29.69	30.25	30.10	30.69	0.245	ns
WS (cm)	9.07	9.71	9.94	9.89	0.169	ns
WB (cm)	11.19	10.94	11.09	11.48	0.194	ns
ACB (cm)	29.44	29.50	29.31	30.19	0.243	ns
PCB (cm)	30.06	29.56	30.00	30.06	0.205	ns
CT (cm)	49.69	48.81	49.75	50.25	0.304	ns
FT (mm)	5.00	5.70	6.83	6.28	0.312	ns
CCI (kg/cm)	0.14	0.14	0.15	0.14	0.002	ns
pH (24 h)	5.94	5.89	5.88	5.88	0.014	ns

• No significant differences ($p > 0.05$) in carcass yields among treatments.

• No significant effect ($p > 0.05$) on carcass conformation and fatness degree.
 • Conformation: **O+** (low-medium muscle development)
 • Fatness degree: **2** (light fat coverage)

• The finishing diet did not significantly ($p > 0.05$) influence the carcass morphometric measurements.

• pH values (**5.88-5.94**) within the acceptable range → normal post-mortem acidification and absence of pre-slaughter stress

SEM: Standard error of the mean; Sig.: significance: ns (not significant). Treatments: CON: Control feed group; BG10: Group supplemented with brewers' grain feed; GP10: Group supplemented with grape pomace feed; OC10: Group supplemented with olive cake feed. IBW: initial live weight (at start of finishing diet); BWS = Live weight at slaughtering; ADG = Average daily gain; HCW = Hot carcass weight; CCW = Cold carcass weight; HCY: Hot carcass yield; CCY: Cold carcass yield; ECL: External carcass length; ICL: Internal carcass length; LL: Leg length; WS: Width of shoulders; WB: Width of buttocks; ACB: Anterior circumference of buttocks; PCB: Posterior circumference of buttocks; CT: Circumference of thorax; FT: Fat thickness; CCI: Carcass compactness index. 1 SEUROP conformation subclasses, in ascending order (P- to S+), were numerically coded from 1 to 18, respectively; 2 Fatness subclasses, in ascending order (1- to 5+), were numerically coded from 1 to 15, respectively.

The inclusion of by-products had **no negative effect** on carcass attributes.

Commercial cutting

Meat cuts (half carcass %)	CON	BG10	GP10	OC10	SEM	Sig.
Leg	25.42	26.62	25.03	25.4	0.319	ns
Ribs	20.36	20.85	20.26	20,13	0.333	ns
Loin	4.67	4.49	5.07	4.45	0.101	ns
Breast	4.05	3.72	3.60	2.87	0.164	ns
Tenderloin	1.53	1.58	1.65	1.71	0.052	ns
Shoulder	14.13	14.2	13.56	13.73	0.164	ns
Neck	6.68	6.74	7.34	7.15	0.165	ns

«High-priced cuts»

SEM: Standard error of the mean; Sig.: significance: ns (not significant). Treatments: CON: Control feed group; BG10: Group supplemented with brewers' grain feed; GP10: Group supplemented with grape pomace feed; OC10: Group supplemented with olive cake feed.

- The yield of the cuts did not show significant differences ($p > 0.05$) compared to the control batch, showing comparable values between the groups.

The commercial value of the carcasses was not compromised by the experimental treatments ($p > 0,05$)

Meat proximate composition and physicochemical attributes

	CON	BG10	GP10	OC10	SEM	Sig.
Proximate composition						
Moisture (g/100 g)	76.17	76.19	76.58	76.57	0.131	ns
Fat (g/100 g)	2.04	2.15	2.05	1.77	0.054	ns
Protein (g/100 g)	20.95	20.73	20.05	20.46	0.126	ns
Ash (g/100 g)	1.19	1.23	1.24	1.17	0.012	ns
Physicochemical parameters						
pH	5.71	5.66	5.71	5.74	0.015	ns
L*	44.07	43.16	44.12	43.82	0.242	ns
a*	10.66	9.8	9.61	10.47	0.166	ns
b*	12.56	11.85	11.81	12.44	0.168	ns
Shear force (N cm ⁻²)	45.45 ^a	44.00 ^a	45.48 ^a	53.51 ^b	1.244	*
Cooking loss (%)	17.80	20.42	21.72	21.70	0.615	ns
DPPH (µg TE/g)	219.86	235.00	248.64	256.81	5.349	ns
TBARs (mg MDA/kg)	0.05	0.05	0.04	0.04	0.002	ns

^{a,b} Mean values in the same row (corresponding to the same parameter) with different letter differ significantly ($P < 0.05$; Duncan test); SEM: Standard error of the mean; Sig.: significance: * ($P < 0.05$); ns (not significant). Treatments: CON: Control feed group; BG10: Group supplemented with brewers' grain feed; GP10: Group supplemented with grape pomace feed; OC10: Group supplemented with olive cake feed.

• No significant differences ($p > 0.05$) in **chemical composition** → balanced diet formulation

• **pH values (5.66-5.74)** within **ideal range** → normal *post-mortem* muscle to meat conversion

• No significant ($p > 0.05$) effects on **meat color** → no adverse impact on myoglobin stability or pigment oxidation

• **Shear force: OC10 > GP10 ≥ CON ≥ BG10** → changes in muscle fiber structure or FA deposition.

• Values ~ **acceptable tenderness thresholds**

• **TBARs values < sensory detection of rancidity** → oxidative stability

The inclusion of by-products had **no negative effect** on meat **chemical composition and physicochemical traits.**

Meat lipid profile

g/100 g FA	CON	BG10	GP10	OC10	SEM	Sig.
SFA	45.24 ^b	45.67 ^b	45.05 ^b	40.25 ^a	0.555	***
MUFA	42.77 ^a	41.80 ^a	41.82 ^a	47.24 ^b	0.491	***
PUFA	12.00	12.53	13.14	12.51	0.318	ns
n-3	1.94	2.07	1.81	1.99	0.079	ns
n-6	9.45	9.82	10.66	9.93	0.254	ns
n-6/n-3	5.00 ^a	4.85 ^a	6.15 ^b	5.10 ^a	0.187	*
PUFA/SFA	0.27	0.28	0.29	0.31	0.009	ns
AI	0.64 ^b	0.67 ^b	0.66 ^b	0.52 ^a	0.016	**
TI	1.36 ^b	1.37 ^b	1.36 ^b	1.12 ^a	0.032	**
h/H	1.84 ^a	1.78 ^a	1.80 ^a	2.29 ^b	0.055	***

^{a,b} Mean values in the same row (corresponding to the same parameter) with different letter differ significantly ($P < 0.05$; Duncan test); SEM: Standard error of the mean; Sig.: significance: *** ($P < 0.001$); ** ($P < 0.01$); * ($P < 0.05$); ns (not significant). Treatments: CON: Control feed group; BG10: Group supplemented with brewers' grain feed; GP10: Group supplemented with grape pomace feed; OC10: Group supplemented with olive cake feed. SFA: Saturated fatty acids; MUFA: Monounsaturated fatty acids; PUFA: Polyunsaturated fatty acids; n-3: Omega-3; n-6: Omega-6; AI: Atherogenic index; TI: Thrombogenic index; h/H: Hypo/hypercholesterolemic ratio.

OC10 ↓ C16:0 ↑ C18:1n-9
GP10 ↑ C18:2n-6

OC10 ↓ SFA ↑ MUFA

OC10 ↓ AI, TI ↑ h/H

OC10 improved lamb meat FA profile and health indices (↑ deposition of healthy FA)

Task 4.2 and 4.3: Main results

Meat sensory profile

Odor and fibrousness unaffected ($p > 0.05$) by diet treatments

↑Tenderness (GP10 ≥ BG10 > OC10 ≥ CON)
 ↑Juiciness (BG10 > GP10 ≥ OC10 ≥ CON)

Alternative dietary treatments enhanced sensorial profile without producing off-flavors (especially BG10)

Task 4.2 and 4.3: Main results

Deliverables

- **D4.1 - Strategies to be tested to improve livestock product** (R, PU; Month 6) (APRI) Planned submission: **September 2026**
- **D4.4 - Efficacy of strategies on animal productivity** (R, CO; Month 29) (APRI) Planned submission: **January 2027**
- **D4.5 - Predictive models for enhanced management** (R, PU; Month 35) (SELMET)

Planned work

Task 5.1 – Multi-dimensional quality of the agro-pastoral food products – Lead: CTC

Work carried out:

- Organization of periodic **meetings** to coordinate the activities to be carried out
- Lamb meat products **elaborations**

Task 5.1: Main results

Parameters	CON-B	GP-B	OC-B	SEM	Sig.
Proximate composition					
Moisture (g/100 g)	62.82 ^a	63.83 ^b	65.05 ^c	0.272	***
Fat (g/100 g)	17.91 ^c	17.21 ^b	15.85 ^a	0.240	***
Protein (g/100 g)	16.60 ^a	16.84 ^{ab}	17.03 ^b	0.061	**
Ash (g/100 g)	1.97	1.97	2.03	0.013	ns
Physicochemical parameters					
pH	6.02 ^a	6.07 ^b	6.00 ^a	0.008	***
L*	53.61	56.45	55.18	0.741	ns
a*	13.59	12.51	13.85	0.422	ns
b*	17.65 ^a	18.77 ^b	18.80 ^b	0.218	*
DPPH (μg TE/g)	136.79 ^a	147.10 ^b	141.89 ^{ab}	1.638	*
TBARs (mg MDA/kg)	0.68 ^b	0.25 ^a	0.77 ^c	0.055	***

- **Fat:** OC-B < GP-B < CON-B → Lean meat from different meat cuts (OC10 meat < fat contents but ns)
- **Moisture:** OC-B > GP-B > CON-B → lower fat content
- **Protein:** CON-B ≤ GP-B < OC-B → Fat obtained from different meat cuts
- **Ash content was not affected**

• The type of diet **did not affect the color except b* values**

- **DPPH:** GP-B ≥ OC-B > CON-B
- **TBARs:** GP-B > OC-B > CON-B → GP lipid oxidation protection (OC > unsaturated FA)
- **TBARs values < sensory threshold limit**

^{a-c} Mean values in the same row (corresponding to the same parameter) with different letter differ significantly (P < 0.05; Duncan test); SEM: Standard error of the mean; Sig.: significance: *** (P < 0.001); ** (P < 0.01); * (P < 0.05); ns (not significant). Treatments: CON-B: Burger from group supplemented with CON feed; GP10: Burger from group supplemented with GP10 feed; OC10: Burger from group supplemented with OC10 feed.

Work carried out:

- Analyzed **how the quality of our lamb-based meat products is constructed, in relation to/considering typicity** (in terms of origin, farmer’s management including feeding system, processing know-how, etc.).

“Notebooks of quality standards for foods containing quality/typicity attributes”

- ❖ Main vectors for typicity of the product (breed, feed, processing among them)
- ❖ Factors strengthening or weakening typicity
- ❖ How a compromise is built combining “uniqueness” and “diversity” in the characteristics of products
- ❖ Impact of diversity on typicity
- ❖ Typicity as a pathway to sustainability

Ongoing work/work carried out:

- **Optimization and extraction of bioactive compounds** from crop, agri-food residues, or herbal spices (e.g. rosemary, olive leaves, pomegranate peel, orange peel) by **emerging technologies** (SFE and UAE), characterization and their **incorporation** process (microencapsulation) (IRA and UIZ)

Optimization of the extraction (UAE) of bioactive compounds from orange peels and of their encapsulation process:

Work carried out and ongoing work:

- Shelf-life study on lambs' burgers pre- and post-intervention (obtained from Task 5.1)

pH and color

Parameters	Day	CON-B	GP-B	OC-B	SEM	T	T × S
pH	0	6.02 ^{aC}	6.07 ^{bC}	6.00 ^{aC}	0.008	***	
	3	5.89 ^{aAB}	6.04 ^{CB}	5.96 ^{bBC}	0.016	***	***
	6	5.90 ^{aB}	6.02 ^{CA}	5.95 ^{bB}	0.012	***	
	9	5.88 ^{aA}	6.02 ^{bA}	5.89 ^{aA}	0.017	***	
	SEM	0.012	0.004	0.010			
	S	***	***	***			
L*	0	53.61 ^B	56.45 ^B	55.18 ^{aB}	0.741	ns	
	3	52.38 ^{abAB}	53.26 ^{bA}	50.04 ^{aA}	0.550	*	ns
	6	50.67 ^{AB}	52.01 ^A	50.85 ^A	0.388	ns	
	9	49.51 ^A	52.56 ^A	50.61 ^A	0.572	ns	
	SEM	0.568	0.558	0.558			
	S	*	*	**			
a*	0	13.59 ^B	12.51 ^B	13.85 ^B	0.422	ns	
	3	12.06 ^{aB}	11.66 ^{aB}	13.99 ^{bB}	0.351	**	ns
	6	9.66 ^A	10.89 ^B	12.13 ^B	0.525	ns	
	9	8.81 ^{bA}	6.59 ^{aA}	9.31 ^{bA}	0.429	*	
	SEM	0.517	0.539	0.527			
	S	***	***	***			
b*	0	17.65 ^{aB}	18.77 ^{bB}	18.80 ^{bB}	0.218	*	
	3	16.57 ^B	17.26 ^A	17.19 ^A	0.236	ns	ns
	6	15.22 ^A	16.50 ^A	16.04 ^A	0.240	ns	
	9	15.03 ^{aA}	16.98 ^{bA}	15.86 ^{abA}	0.333	*	
	SEM	0.297	0.236	0.323			
	S	***	***	***			

• **GP-B > CON-B > OC-B** and more stable during storage → diet effect on muscle metabolism and glycogen stores + **different carcass cuts and stress of processing**

Storage time:

- ↓ L* → ↓ moisture and ↑ oxidation (day 3: **OC-B** ≤ **CON-B** ≤ **GP-B** → **OC-B** < meat fat content and **GP-B** > pH)
- ↓ a* (over day 9 except **CON-B** day 6) → myoglobin oxidation (day 3 and 9: **GP-B** < **CON-B** ≤ **OC-B** → metabolic interaction after meat processing)
- ↓ b* → general degradation (day 9: **GP-B** > **OC-B** ≥ **CON-B** → preserve pigment intensity)

^{a-c} Mean values in the same row (corresponding to the same treatment) not followed by the same letter differ significantly (influence of treatment) (P < 0.05; Duncan test); ^{A-C} Mean values in the same column (corresponding to the same day) not followed by the same letter differ significantly (influence of storage day) (P < 0.05; Duncan test); T: Treatment effect; S: Storage effect; SEM: Standard error of the mean; Sig.: significance: *** (P < 0.001); ** (P < 0.01); * (P < 0.05); ns (not significant). Treatments: CON-B: Burger from group supplemented with CON feed; BG10: Burger from group supplemented with BG10 feed; GP10: Burger from group supplemented with GP10 feed; OC10: Burger from group supplemented with OC10 feed.

Task 5.4: Main results

DPPH

- Storage time ↓ DPPH values
- GP-B ≥ OC-B > CON-B by the end of storage → dietary phenols transfer into the meat

TBARS

- Storage time ↑ TBARS values
- GP-B < CON-B < OC-B → strongly inhibited oxidation → ↑ antioxidant deposition (OC-B chemically unstable fats ↑ UFA)

GP10 robust protection against the oxidative stress typical of retail burger production → high efficacy in preventing chemical rancidity

WP5 deliverables are focused on the quality and safety of **processed dairy and meat products**:

-
D5.1 - Quality and safety of the agro-pastoral products from living labs pre-intervention (R, PU; Month 15) (CTC): Focuses on traditional **dairy and meat products** obtained from milk/meat before the implementation of any improvement strategies in the living labs. Deadline: **August 2025** Planned submission: **2026**

- D5.2 - At least 3 banks of indigenous bacteriocinogenic and probiotic lactic acid bacteria from selected agropastoral products (R, CO; Month 25) (IRA) (not involved)**
-
D5.3 - Quality of newly developed functional food products (R, PU; Month 27) (CTC): Covers **innovative and functional dairy and meat products** developed during the project. Deadline: **October 2025** Planned submission: **2027**

- D5.4 - Shelf-life predictive models of current agro-pastoral food products and newly-developed functional food products (DEM, PU; Month 33) (IPB) (pending template – shelf-life)**

-
D5.5 - Quality and safety of the agro-pastoral products from living labs post-intervention (R, PU; Month 35) (CTC): Includes **dairy/meat products** derived from milk/meat after implementing improvement strategies in the living labs. Planned submission: **2026**

- D5.6 - Notebooks of quality standards for foods containing quality/typicity attributes (R, PU; Month 32) (SELMET)**

Task 5.1 - Multi-dimensional quality of the agro-pastoral food products:

- Elaboration of **goat meat-derived meat products (pre- and post-intervention)** and quality analysis
- Collection of information (reports) from the other partners, working with sheep, goats, camelids and evaluating the quality of meat- and dairy-origin products, to complete **deliverable 5.1** (successively **5.5**)

Task 5.2 - Typicity and differentiation of the agro-pastoral food products:

- Analyze how the **quality of goat-based meat products** is constructed considering **typicity**.

Task 5.3 - Development of innovative agro-pastoral food products:

- Elaboration of **functional high-value lamb and goat meat products, and their characterization**: incorporation of **natural antioxidant** sources in burgers, and/or **dietary fiber** sources in dry-fermented sausages
- **Collection of information** (reports) from the other partners (IRA, UIZ, UNISS, and ITACyL), developing innovative agri-pastoral food products (to complete the **deliverable 5.3**)

Task 5.4 - Shelf-life of agro-pastoral food products:

- Shelf-life study on **lamb** (obtained from Task 5.3) and **goat-derived meat products** (obtained from Task 5.1 and 5.3)

Dissemination and communication of the results

Task 6.3 - E-commerce platform

Publish a minimum **viable catalogue of agro-pastoral products and services**, enabling short value chains and visibility for living-lab producers.

It will commence once **WP5 product specifications** and WP7 platform modules are established.

WP Nº	8		Lead beneficiary					UIZ			
WP title	Training, communication and dissemination										
Short name	IPB	ECoE	APRI	SELMET	MoSAR	UNISS	IAV	UIZ	CTC	ITACyL	IRA
OM/participant	6	6	7	1.2	2.3	2.5	1.5	12.6	3	2	2
Start month	1				End month			36			

Communication/dissemination activities

Work carried out:

Participation to Congress:

- “Efecto de la alimentación sobre los parámetros productivos de corderos de raza Ovella Galega”, “XXVI Simposio Iberoamericano sobre Conservación de Recursos Zootenéticos Criollos y Autóctonos (REGAD 2025)”, Montería y Cereté, Córdoba, Colombia (22-24/10/2025)
- “Essential oil extraction using a supercritical CO2 extraction system and its impact on the antioxidant capacity of *Matricaria chamomilla* L.” 10th Edition of the International Research School (EIR), Agadir, Marruecos (11-13/12/2025)
- “Effect of agri-food by-products on the lipid profile of *Ovella Galega* lamb meat” NUTRICON 2026, Ohrid, Macedonia (03-05/06/2026) (accepted)

Scientific publications:

- “Influence of agro-industrial by-products inclusion on growth parameters and carcass quality in *Ovella Galega* lambs”
- “Effect of the use of agro-industrial by-products on the meat quality in Galician lambs” (work in process)

October 2025

EFFECTO DE LA ALIMENTACIÓN SOBRE LOS PARAMETROS PRODUCTIVOS DE CORDEROS DE RAZA OVELLA GALEGA

EFFECT OF FEEDING ON THE PRODUCTIVE PARAMETERS OF OVELLA GALEGA LAMBS

Aurora Cittadini¹, Roberto Bermúdez¹, Silvia Adán², Bernardino Domínguez³, Iguel Fernández⁴, José M. Lorenzo^{1,4}

December 2025

10th Edition of the International Research School (EIR) “Biotechnological Innovations and Agroecological Resilience: Towards Sustainable and Inclusive Mediterranean Territories”

Oral presentation

Essential oil extraction using a supercritical CO₂ extraction system and its impact on the antioxidant capacity of *Matricaria chamomilla* L.

Hanza Tami¹, Jose Manuel Lorenzo^{2,3}, Roberto Bermúdez Piedra², Aurora Cittadini², Said Elhizazi¹, Fouad Achemchem¹

March 2026

Article

Influence of Agro-Industrial By-Products Inclusion on Growth Parameters and Carcass Quality in *Ovella Galega* Lambs

Aurora Cittadini¹, Roberto Bermúdez¹, Vasco Cadavez^{2,3}, Adriana González-Peaguda¹, Raúl Bodas³ and José Manuel Lorenzo^{1,4,5,6}

WP 8. Training, communication and dissemination – Lead: UIZ

Work carried out:

Social media:

- 4 Publications on PAS-AGRO-PAS social media (Facebook and Instagram), and reposted on the CTC social network (Facebook and LinkedIn) on our advances and activities:
 - 2nd Face-to-face PAS-AGRO-PAS meeting
 - Start of the CTC's animal trails and ITACyL visit (WP4-5)
 - UIZ knowledge exchange at CTC (WP5)
 - Publication of the scientific article on Animals Journal (WP3-4)

Stakeholder dissemination event:

- Presentation of PAS-AGRO-PAS project results during the Meat sector working group of the “Food for Life-Spain Technological Platform (PTF4LS)” (March 2026)

Knowledge exchange activities:

- UIZ 3-months knowledge exchange at CTC (WP5)

May 2025

July 2025

September 2025

March 2026

March 2026

June-September 2025

Scientific publications:

- "Effect of the feeding type on the meat quality of Galician lamb"
- "Influence of the finishing diet on the productive parameters and carcass quality of Galician goat"
- "Impact of agro-industrial by-products on meat quality in *Cabra Galega* goats"
- "Shelf-life improvement of sheep burgers enriched with natural antioxidants"
- "Shelf-life evaluation of goat patties formulated with natural antioxidants"
- "Development of functional dry-fermented lamb sausages"

Participation to Congress:

- NUTRICON 2026, Ohrid, Macedonia (03-05/06/2026) (1 communication)
- 72nd International Congress of Meat Science and Technology (ICOMST 2026), Daejeon, Korea (9-14/08/2026) (2 communications)
- International Conference on Food Science and Nutrition (ICFSN 2027), Prague, Czechia (22-23/03/2027)

Workshop-activity:

- Workshop on "Valorization strategies of sheep and goat: functional products."

Social media:

- Social media update on the progress of CTC activities

NUTRICON

2026
ICOMST
72nd International Congress of Meat Science and Technology
August 9-14 DAEJEON, KOREA

CTC contribution

Breed and meat valorization: Assessment of **productive parameters, carcass and meat quality** of **Galician lambs** and **goat** breeds under dietary upcycling. **Development and study of traditional and novel functional meat products;**

- **Technical support:** provision of experimental data and reports to support the execution and completion of Work Package activities;
- **Dissemination:** continuous communication of **CTC project activities and results** through **publications, events, and social media.**

Strategic needs from Consortium

- More frequent **communication and update** cycles among task leaders and all partners;
- Guidance and delivery templates from Task Leaders to support the completion of pending deliverables;
- Timely submission of reports and inputs from all partners to the completion and submission of **deliverables 5.1, 5.3, and 5.5.**

Thank you for your attention

More information about us:

www.ceteca.net

Unit of UNISS-Department of Agricultural Science

NAME	Role in PRIMA	Area of research
Antonello Cannas	-Coordinator of the Unit of UNISS -Leader WP6 -participant all other WP	Prof. Animal nutrition and feeding
Rosella Motzo	WP3	Prof. Agronomy and cultivated crops
Francesco Giunta	WP3	Prof. Agronomy and cultivated crops
Maria Caria	WP4	Prof. Agriculture mechanical engineering
Giuseppe Todde	WP4	Prof. Agriculture mechanical engineering
Anna Nudda	WP5	Prof. Animal science
Nicoletta Mangia	WP5	Prof. Milk & cheese microbiology
Luciano Gutierrez	WP2-WP6	Prof. Agricultural economics
Maria Sabbagh	WP2-WP6	Post.doc. Agricultural economics

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**WP 3. Enhanced productivity, adaptiveness and
 diversification of crops, pastures, forages**
**3.1.1. Lupin and faba bean as a source of
 protein in rainfed cropping systems of
 Mediterranean environments**
3.1.2. Dual-purpose use of cereals
**3. 5. Predictive models for lupin and faba
 bean**

- Rosella Motzo
- Francesco Giunta

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3.1.2. Dual-purpose use of cereals

- Dual purpose use: grazing at the end of tillering/onset of stem elongation + harvest of grains and straw in the same season
- Advantages of dual-purpose: filling the gap in herbage availability in winter, flexibility, sustainability
- Old and tall durum wheat cvs such as S.Cappelli can be suited to this type of utilization
- **Results:**
- A 2-year field trial revealed that the lateness, tallness and high vigour of old tall durum wheat cultivars could be advantageous for dual-purpose use
- Grazing until the onset of stem elongation can reduce lodging
- Grain yield was not affected by grazing because animals did not damage the growing spike

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3.1.1. Lupin and faba bean as a source of protein in rainfed cropping systems of Mediterranean environments

A manuscript is ready for submission

Comparative Performance, Resource Use Efficiency, and Yield Stability of White Lupin and Faba Bean under Mediterranean Conditions

Abstract

Grain legumes are essential for enhancing the sustainability of European agroecosystems, yet their cultivation remains limited, contributing to reliance on imported protein sources. This study evaluates the agronomic performance, resource use efficiency, and yield stability of white lupin (*Lupinus albus* L.) and faba bean (*Vicia faba* L.) under Mediterranean conditions. An eight-year field experiment (2013–2022) was conducted in Sardinia, Italy, comparing the two species under varying seasonal conditions and row spacing (0.25 vs 0.50 m). Biomass production, grain yield, yield components, nitrogen accumulation, radiation interception, and water use efficiency were assessed.

Faba bean generally produced higher biomass and exhibited greater water-use efficiency, while grain yield differences between species were inconsistent across years due to strong environmental interactions. Lupin showed greater yield variability, largely driven by fluctuations in seed number, indicating higher plasticity. **Lupin** demonstrated higher grain nitrogen concentration and nitrogen harvest index, resulting in superior grain protein content compared to faba bean. Conversely, faba bean allocated more nitrogen to vegetative biomass and maintained more efficient water use for both biomass and grain production.

Reduced inter-row spacing increased biomass and grain yield in both species, with a stronger relative response observed in lupin, leading to comparable yields between the two species at narrower spacing. Seasonal rainfall distribution, particularly spring water availability, remained the main determinant of crop performance.

Overall, the results highlight complementary strengths of the two legumes: **faba bean for yield stability and efficient water use, and lupin for protein concentration and nitrogen allocation to grain**. These findings support the integration of both species into Mediterranean cropping systems to enhance diversification, resilience, and sustainability.

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3.5 Predictive models for lupin and faba bean

Models can be used to simulate the growth and development of lupin and faba bean in order to analyse their year to year variability in terms of biomass, yield and N uptake for both the past (thanks to a 50-year weather data-set for two sites in Sardinia, Italy) and the future.

- Essential parameters related to phenology, radiation interception and radiation-use efficiency, water use and water-use efficiency have been derived from the 8-year field trials
- Essential parameters will be used with to run two types of models:

APSIM (Farrè et al., 2004; Chen et al., 2017; Turpin et al., 2003)

*Grain yield = Intercepted radiation
x Radiation-use efficiency x
Harvest Index*

Only parameters for narrow-leafed lupin (*L. angustifolius* L.) in Western Australia are currently available

AQUACROP (Raes et al., 2009)

*Grain yield = Water transpired x
Water-use efficiency x Harvest
Index*

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WP 4. Enhanced productivity, adaptiveness and diversification of crops, pastures, forages

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DIGITAL SYSTEM DEVELOPED

Maria Caria – Giuseppe Todde

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THE SMART WEARABLE READER

The Smart Reader (LS) is a prototype developed for the electronic identification of animals on farms using RFID (radio frequency identification) technology, integrated with the HoloLens 2 augmented reality headsets

Main components

- Control unit with Bluetooth
- RFID Reader + Antenna (125 - 134 kHz)
- Vibration sensor
- 3D printed wearable case

Operating steps:

1. Reads RFID tag
2. Send the animal's ID code to the augmented reality headset

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EVALUATION AND VALIDATION TEST

On-Field test

Laboratory test

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LABORATORY RESULTS

DISTANZA (cm)	SMART READER	CONTROL READER
	%	%
20	0	0
15	0	0
12	0	3.33
11	0	40.1
10	0	100
9	0	100
8	26.7	100
7	66.7	100
6	80.0	100
5	98.5	100
4	100	100
3	100	100
2	100	100
1	100	100

•The maximum reading distance in laboratory for smart reader is 5 cm, with a 100 % success rate

•Control reader, the maximum reading distance is 10 cm with a 100 % success rate

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ON FIELD RESULTS: AUGMENTED REALITY INTERFACE

Here you can see the digital system operating directly inside the barn. Once the operator wears the augmented reality headset and the Smart Reader on the wrist, he can identify the animals in front of him.

After launching the AR application, the animal is scanned, and the associated data are displayed in real time, retrieved from the cloud.

As shown, the operator can interact directly with the holograms generated by the headset, without the need for any handheld controller.

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WP 4. Enhanced productivity, adaptiveness and diversification of crops, pastures, forages

Effects of individual concentrate doses according to milk yield of ewes

Porcu M.A., Castangia F., Ledda A., Cannas A. EAAP Regional Meeting 2026, 20-22 May 2026 - Sassari, Italy

Hypotheses

Sheep fed **individual doses of concentrates**, proportional to their milk yield, would be more productive or efficient

Material and methods

22 ewes in the 3rd- 4th month of lactation were divided into two homogeneous groups based on weight, BCS, milk yield and milk fat content (%):

CONTROL (11 ewes) → Grazing for **9 hours** + **fixed dose of concentrates (600 g/d corn grain)** calculated on the basis of the average requirements of the group;

TREATMENT (11 ewes) → Grazing for **9 hours** + **individual concentrate dose** (corn grain) calculated on the basis of the milk yield of each ewes of the group.

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WP 4. Enhanced productivity, adaptiveness and diversification of crops, pastures, forages

Conclusions

The supply of **individual doses of corn grains (starchy feed) based on the production level** of ewes in the third or fourth month of lactation:

- did not result in significant changes in milk production or composition
- did not result in changes in feeding behavior
- promoted an increase in the energy balance (body reserve accumulation)

During this stage of lactation, the **ewes fed individual doses of corn grains, a starch-rich concentrate, partitioned the energy in favor of body reserves rather than extra milk production**, in accordance with the study conducted by Lunesu et al. (2021) who suggested that this might depend by the high insulin levels observed in sheep after few months of lactation

It is likely that during this stage of lactation, the supply of individual doses of feeds rich in **digestible fiber**, such as beet pulps or soybean hulls, could have elicited a favorable response in terms of milk production

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Effects of feeding time on milk production and composition in Sarda ewes

F. Castangia, M. A. Porcu, A. Ledda, A. S. Atzori, A. Cannas AEAAP Regional Meeting 2026, 20-22 May 2026 - Sassari, Italy

In dairy ruminants, with equal intervals (12 h +12 h) milk production shows a **daily pattern**: similar milk yield in the morning and evening milkings, but **lower fat and protein concentrations** in the morning compared with evening milking: **Why?**

OBJECTIVE

To evaluate the effect of different **feeding times** on **milk fat and protein concentrations** in dairy sheep milked at 12-hour intervals

METHODS Biocontrol AS mangers (Rakkestad, Norway)

Animals are divided into **3 treatment groups**:

DAY Group: Feed available for sheep from 7:00 a.m. to 7:00 p.m.;

NIGHT Group: Feed available for sheep from 7:00 p.m. to 7:00 a.m.;

CONTROL Group: Feed available for sheep in 24 hours.

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RESULTS

Same daily milk production in NIGHT and DAY, higher in CONTROL

Higher milk fat and protein % in the morning milking for NIGHT feeding

Higher milk fat and protein % in the evening milking for DAY feeding

The low milk fat and protein % usually observed in the morning milking is due to the **limited intake of feed during the night**

It seems that the **priority for the ewes is milk volume, milk fat and protein second priority**

Technical solutions are available

Milk	DAY	NIGHT
Milk Yield (g/d)	1745 ^b	1732 ^b
Morning Milk Yield (g/milking)	912 ^b	909 ^b
Evening Milk Yield (g/milking)	833 ^b	822 ^b

Different lowercase letters in the same row indicate differences for $P < 0.05$

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WP 5. Valorisation of agro-pastoral food products Use of grape pomace in the diet of dairy sheep

Anna Nudda, Nicoletta Mangia, Silvia Carta

Objectives

The aims of this study were to evaluate the effect of the supplementation of **Grape Pomace (GP)** in the diet of ewes during the mid-lactation on milk composition, on Fruhe/Casu axedu production and its fatty acids profile

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Why Grape pomace?

- ✓ Grape pomace is a by-product of the wine industry that contains **polyphenols** and fatty acids that could improve the animal product quality

	Grape	
	Mean	Min-Max
By-product from processes, %	22	20-25
Moisture, %	71.2	63.0-81.7
<i>Chemical composition</i>		
Dry matter, % as fed	92.0	88.6-95.0
Protein, % DM	12.0	8.8-16.3
Fat, % DM	6.6	3.9-11.4
NDF, % DM	42.4	37.4-53.9
ADF, % DM	36.6	30.6-49.2
Ash, % DM	7.7	2.1-12.1
Total polyphenol, g/kg DM	35.9	3-90
<i>Main fatty acids (% on total FA)</i>		
Palmitic acid	9.6	5.5-12.5
Stearic acid	4.3	2.8-4.9
Oleic acid	15.2	9.6-19.2
Linoleic acid	56.9	51.1-74.0
Alpha linolenic acid	1.4	0.2-3.7

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Why Fruhe/Casu Axedu?

- Traditional fresh cheese (**actually** acid –curd) from Sardinia (Italy)
- Known locally as Casu axedu
- Consumed for centuries and by centenarians
- Appreciated for its fresh, tangy flavor

Fruhe is the only fresh cheese made from sheep's milk, registered in the list of Italian Traditional Food Products (PAT), MASAF.

The basic requirement to be included in such a list refers to the method of processing, preservation and ageing consolidated over time, which must be linked to traditional rules, for a defined time that cannot be less than twenty-five years.

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WP 5. Valorisation of agro-pastoral food products

Use of grape pomace in the diet of dairy sheep

Material and Methods

- The study was conducted at the experimental farm of the Dipartimento di Agraria, University of Sassari
- Ewes were kept together in a barn equipped with 10 individual automatic feeding systems (Biocontrol AS, Rakkestad, Norway), and the **individual feed intake** was daily recorded

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WP 5. Valorisation of agro-pastoral food products

use of grape pomace in the diet of dairy sheep

Materials & Methods: Animals and Diet

24 Sarda dairy sheep were divided in three groups homogeneous for:

- ❖ Body weight, **BW**, 58.0 ± 0.75 kg
- ❖ Milk yield, **MY**, 2.4 ± 0.007 kg
- ❖ Days in milk, **DIM**, 101 ± 1 day

Control group: CON

Total mixed ration without any supplementation

Treatment group: LOW-GP

Total mixed ration supplemented with **100 g/d** per head of GP

Treatment group: HIGH-GP

Total mixed ration supplemented with **150 g/d** per head of GP

The byproduct administrated individually in the self-locking

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Material and Methods: **Laboratory analysis**

Feed samples
were analyzed for:

- Dry matter intake
- Crude protein
- NDF
- ADF
- ADL
- Ash

milk
samples were analyzed for:

- Composition
- FA

Milk and Frue samples
were analyzed for:

- Gross Composition
- Fatty acid
- Microbial

2
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2. **Lactic Acid Bacteria count during Frue storage**

We observed the suitability of milk as a substrate for the growth and maintenance of both technological and potentially beneficial microbes.

pH value was < 4.2 in all groups

At 21 days of cold storage

- Both lactobacilli and streptococci remained stable throughout 21 days of cold storage.
- Lactic streptococci in Frue D100 was higher than D150

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WP 5. Valorisation of agro-pastoral food products

Fruhe fatty acid profile

FA, g/100 g of FAME	Groups		
	CON	LOW-GP	HIGH-GP
SFA	76.10	75.98	74.54
UFA	23.74	23.87	25.30
MUFA	18.98	19.03	20.11
PUFA	4.76	4.84	5.19
BCFA	2.29	2.19	2.08
OCFA	3.26	3.07	2.99
Total CLA	0.58	0.51	0.71
C18_1t11	0.74	0.68	1.04
CLAc9t11	0.45	0.38	0.56
C18_3n3	0.48	0.49	0.46

SFA

PUFA

Fruhe /casu Axedu: GP supplementation decrease significantly the SFA and increase the UFA

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WP 5. Valorisation of agro-pastoral food products

Individual fatty acid in Fruhe/Casu axedu

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Results: Methane emissions

Group	Concentration, ppm*m	P-Value
CON	45.3	ns
LOW-GROUP	40.2	ns
HIGH-GROUP	48.8	ns

no differences between groups were observed

WP 5. Valorisation of agro-pastoral food products

Results

- the chemical composition of the milk of GP groups was suitable as control group for *fruhe* production;
- no adverse effects were observed on fermentation performance or Fruhe consistency due to GP supplementation;
- the total microbial count (live bacteria) was > 8 log CFU/g 21 days of conservation;
- the pH value was < 4.2 in all groups;
- the inclusion of grape pomace at the highest dose significantly reduced Saturated Fatty Acids (SFA) and increased;
- Fruhe/Casu axedu D150 showed the highest levels of CLA and vaccenic acid;
- regarding the methane emissions, we found no differences between groups.

WP 6. Enhanced economic and social conditions for agro-pastoralism livelihoods

Leader of WP6: Antonello Cannas UNISS; Main participant: Prof. Luciano Gutierrez (Agricultural Economics)

OBJECTIVES

Task 6.1. Studies for pricing and economic profitability of agro-pastoral systems. To fully transmit along the links of the food chains the implicit value of the agro-pastoral products, attending to the assured quality and typicity of the agro-pastoral products (linked to WP5);

Task 6.2. To establish policy guidelines for value chain stakeholders combined with integrated strategic planning;

TASK 6.3. The e-commerce platform. To promote the commercialization mentality among agro-pastoralists by training and promotion (linked to WP8) and by the construction of the PAS-AGRO-PAS e-commerce platform.

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WP 6. Enhanced economic and social conditions for agro-pastoralism livelihoods

Willingness to Pay for Traditional Cheese in the Context of Rural Heritage and Market Competition

Luciano Gutierrez (*), Maria Sabbagh (**)

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(**) Department of Agricultural Sciences, University of Sassari, Viale Italia 39/B, Sassari, Italy: msabbagh@uniss.it

Abstract

This study examines whether consumers are willing to pay a premium for traditionally produced cheese and explores how this behaviour supports the resilience of rural production systems. Combining a Bertrand duopoly model with the Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB), we analyse whether traditional producers—despite higher production costs and competition from industrial firms—can economically sustain higher prices. Data were collected from 1,640 Italian consumers, including a representative sample from Sardinia, and analysed using PLS-SEM. Fiore Sardo PDO cheese was used as a case study.

Attitudes, subjective norms and perceived behavioural control significantly influenced consumers' willingness to buy, which in turn predicted willingness to pay a premium. On average, consumers were willing to pay €3.70 more per kg in Sardinia and €5.50 elsewhere in Italy. These findings show that traditional foods are valued not only for their sensory qualities but also for their cultural significance and capacity to support rural livelihoods and heritage.

The study contributes to rural studies by demonstrating that traditional agrifood systems can remain competitive when consumers associate them with authenticity, social value and territorial identity. Policy and marketing strategies should therefore reinforce origin labelling, producer recognition and cultural communication.

Keywords: Traditional foods, Industrial competition, PDO, Theory of Planned Behaviour, Willingness to pay.

TASK 6.1: Studies for pricing and economic profitability of agro-pastoral systems

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Keywords: CONSUMER BEHAVIOUR · RURAL DEVELOPMENT · AGRIFOOD MARKETING

Valuing Tradition: Consumer Willingness to Pay a Premium for Traditional Cheese

This study combines a **Bertrand duopoly model** with the **Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB)** to examine whether consumers are willing to pay more for traditionally produced cheese — and whether that willingness can economically sustain rural production systems. Using **Fiore Sardo PDO** as a case study, we analyse survey data from **1,640 Italian consumers**, including a representative sample from Sardinia, via PLS-SEM.

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What Drives Consumers to Pay More?

Three TPB constructs significantly influenced consumers' willingness to buy, which in turn predicted their willingness to pay a premium for Fiore Sardo PDO.

Attitudes

Positive evaluations of traditional cheese's sensory qualities and cultural meaning drove purchase intent.

1,640

Consumers Surveyed

Across Italy, including a representative Sardinian sample

Subjective Norms

Perceived social expectations — from family, community, and cultural identity — reinforced buying behaviour.

€3.70

Premium in Sardinia

Average additional willingness to pay per kg among local consumers

Perceived Behavioural Control

Consumers' sense of access and affordability shaped their ability to act on purchase intentions.

€5.50

Premium Elsewhere

Average additional willingness to pay per kg among consumers in mainland Italy

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Task 6.2 – Policy guidelines for value chain stakeholders with integrated strategic planning

Implications for Rural Resilience and Policy

Traditional agrifood systems can remain competitive when consumers associate them with **authenticity, social value, and territorial identity**.

These findings carry direct implications for policy and marketing.

For Policymakers

- Strengthen origin labelling frameworks (e.g., PDO) to signal authenticity.
- Invest in producer recognition schemes that reward traditional practices.

For Producers & Marketers

- Communicate territorial identity and cultural significance, not just product attributes.
- Leverage subjective norms by highlighting the community and heritage connections.
- Target both local and national markets — mainland consumers show higher premiums.

Key Insight: Traditional foods are valued not only for sensory qualities but for their capacity to support rural livelihoods and cultural heritage — a positioning that justifies premium pricing and sustains small-scale production.

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TASK 6.3: The e-commerce platform

Next activities: multimedial labels on Fiore Sardo and Fruhe

- essential **basic information** for **quick users** (e.g. shopping customer): origin, basic nutritional analysis
- more **in dept information** (e.g. videos, detailed analysis and evaluations, “story telling”) for **demanding customers**

EXAMPLE

<https://www.granmoravia.com/?s=etichetta+multimediale&lang=it>

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Thank for the attention

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Classification of Sheep Forage Resources in the Steppes of Eastern Morocco Using Near-Infrared Spectroscopy (NIRS)

**Taha Nour
Abdelilah Araba
Soufiane El Aayadi**

Table of contents

- 01.* • Context
- 02.* • Aims and goals of the study
- 03.* • Methodology
- 04.* • Results and discussion
- 05.* • Conclusions
- 06.* • What's next ?

Context

What is the nutritional composition of forage pastoral species?

Is the NIRS method reliable for predicting the nutritional value of forage pastoral species?

To what extent does shepherds' perception of the nutritional quality of forage species serve as a reliable and relevant decision-making tool for herd management?

Aims and Goals

Methodology

Study area

Location and Administrative Boundaries of the Oriental Region (QGIS)

Study area

3.2 millions
hectares
(Bechchari et al., 2014)

3.2 to 3.5 millions
sheep
(MAPDREF, 2024)

Activities

Work Blueprint

Surveys and sample collection

Chemical analysis

Biochemical Composition(n=20) :

-Dry matter;

-Fiber:

- Crude Fiber(Wendee)
- NDF, ADF, ADL (Van Soest)

-Crude Protein(Kjeldahl);

-Ash(Incineration).

Source : AOAC International. Official Methods of Analysis (Volume 1), 1990.

NIRS analysis

ID	DM %	ASH %	CP %	EE %	CF %	NDF %	ADF %	ADL %	MDCELL %	OMDCELL %	STARCH %	SUGARS %
1	91.77	8.27	16.38	3.8	27.57	63.7	30.4	3.08	60.02	57.57	4.57	7.55
2	92.38	9.37	17.74	5.43	25.55	58.35	26.79	3.2	65.89	62.94	2.92	6.18
3	91.41	9.56	18.12	4.61	23.55	53.16	24.54	2.29	74.22	72.11	3.71	8.11
4	91.77	8.27	16.38	3.8	27.57	63.7	30.4	3.08	60.02	57.57	4.57	7.55
5	92.38	9.37	17.74	5.43	25.55	58.35	26.79	3.2	65.89	62.94	2.92	6.18
6	91.41	9.56	18.12	4.61	23.55	53.16	24.54	2.29	74.22	72.11	3.71	8.11
7	91.77	8.27	16.38	3.8	27.57	63.7	30.4	3.08	60.02	57.57	4.57	7.55
8	92.38	9.37	17.74	5.43	25.55	58.35	26.79	3.2	65.89	62.94	2.92	6.18
9	91.41	9.56	18.12	4.61	23.55	53.16	24.54	2.29	74.22	72.11	3.71	8.11
10	91.77	8.27	16.38	3.8	27.57	63.7	30.4	3.08	60.02	57.57	4.57	7.55
11	92.38	9.37	17.74	5.43	25.55	58.35	26.79	3.2	65.89	62.94	2.92	6.18
12	91.41	9.56	18.12	4.61	23.55	53.16	24.54	2.29	74.22	72.11	3.71	8.11
13	91.77	8.27	16.38	3.8	27.57	63.7	30.4	3.08	60.02	57.57	4.57	7.55
14	92.38	9.37	17.74	5.43	25.55	58.35	26.79	3.2	65.89	62.94	2.92	6.18
15	91.41	9.56	18.12	4.61	23.55	53.16	24.54	2.29	74.22	72.11	3.71	8.11
16	91.77	8.27	16.38	3.8	27.57	63.7	30.4	3.08	60.02	57.57	4.57	7.55
17	92.38	9.37	17.74	5.43	25.55	58.35	26.79	3.2	65.89	62.94	2.92	6.18
18	91.41	9.56	18.12	4.61	23.55	53.16	24.54	2.29	74.22	72.11	3.71	8.11
19	91.77	8.27	16.38	3.8	27.57	63.7	30.4	3.08	60.02	57.57	4.57	7.55
20	92.38	9.37	17.74	5.43	25.55	58.35	26.79	3.2	65.89	62.94	2.92	6.18
21	91.41	9.56	18.12	4.61	23.55	53.16	24.54	2.29	74.22	72.11	3.71	8.11
22	91.77	8.27	16.38	3.8	27.57	63.7	30.4	3.08	60.02	57.57	4.57	7.55
23	92.38	9.37	17.74	5.43	25.55	58.35	26.79	3.2	65.89	62.94	2.92	6.18
24	91.41	9.56	18.12	4.61	23.55	53.16	24.54	2.29	74.22	72.11	3.71	8.11
25	91.77	8.27	16.38	3.8	27.57	63.7	30.4	3.08	60.02	57.57	4.57	7.55
26	92.38	9.37	17.74	5.43	25.55	58.35	26.79	3.2	65.89	62.94	2.92	6.18
27	91.41	9.56	18.12	4.61	23.55	53.16	24.54	2.29	74.22	72.11	3.71	8.11
28	91.77	8.27	16.38	3.8	27.57	63.7	30.4	3.08	60.02	57.57	4.57	7.55
29	92.38	9.37	17.74	5.43	25.55	58.35	26.79	3.2	65.89	62.94	2.92	6.18
30	91.41	9.56	18.12	4.61	23.55	53.16	24.54	2.29	74.22	72.11	3.71	8.11
31	91.77	8.27	16.38	3.8	27.57	63.7	30.4	3.08	60.02	57.57	4.57	7.55
32	92.38	9.37	17.74	5.43	25.55	58.35	26.79	3.2	65.89	62.94	2.92	6.18
33	91.41	9.56	18.12	4.61	23.55	53.16	24.54	2.29	74.22	72.11	3.71	8.11
34	91.77	8.27	16.38	3.8	27.57	63.7	30.4	3.08	60.02	57.57	4.57	7.55
35	92.38	9.37	17.74	5.43	25.55	58.35	26.79	3.2	65.89	62.94	2.92	6.18

Web Platform @DoPredict

User: Lionel Julien
 Input file: 40 Spectres.csv
 No samples: 40
 Date: 2024-04-05 12:26:31
 Database: plants feed selmet

UMR 1213 Hélios
 Systèmes d'élevage
 durable

Variables	Content	Unit	Abbreviation	Reference method	Variable	Mean	Min	Max	N
Dry matter	%	DM		105 degrees Celsius, 24 hours	DM	92.24	81.45	99.97	18255
Mineral matter	%	ASH		500 degrees Celsius, 4 hours	ASH	9.75	0.04	99.96	17839
Cruze protein	NDM	CP		Nitrogen 6.25	CP	14.90	0.20	98.45	16840
Cruze fat	NDM	EE		Extracted by petroleum ether	EE	5.71	0.08	69.42	7243
Cruze fiber	NDM	CF		Weende method	CF	25.86	0.06	77.87	13232
Neutral detergent fiber	NDM	NDF		Van Soest Method	NDF	51.89	0.61	96.07	10677
Acid detergent fiber	NDM	ADF		Van Soest Method	ADF	33.27	0.14	85.80	11360
Acid detergent lignin	NDM	ADL		Van Soest Method	ADL	8.28	0.01	50.77	11072
In vitro dry matter enzymatic digestibility	NDM	DMOCELL		Aufere peptin-cellulase method	DMOCELL	52.52	6.58	99.08	9187
In vitro organic matter enzymatic digestibility	NDM	OMDCELL		Aufere peptin-cellulase method	OMDCELL	50.38	6.18	99.59	8857
Starch	NDM	STARCH		Potimetry Iwers method	STARCH	31.67	0.04	88.94	2020
Total sugars	NDM	SUGARS		Luff-Schoorj method	SUGARS	7.99	0.05	75.57	2123

About Details

Predictions and indicators of validity

The validity of a prediction can be assessed with the 3 following indicators

OutX: Distance index between the spectrum to predict and the center of its selected neighborhood
 Lower is better

DensY: Density index of observed Y-values around the Y-prediction
 Higher is better

OutY: indicates if the Y-prediction is outside the range of the observed Y-values

If OutX or OutY are out of range, the sample cell has a colored background →

Index	Value	Color value
OutX	<= 1.5	OK
OutX	> 1.5	OutXFull
DensY	<= 0.5	OK
DensY	> 0.5	OutY
OutY	empty	OK
OutY	OutY	OutYFull

UMR Selmet <https://umr-selmet.cirad.fr/>
 Contact depredict@cirad.fr

Results

Results

Proportion of the different biological types of pastoral plants

■ Herbaceous plants ■ Shrubs ■ Small trees

Proportion of annual and perennial species in the pastoral flora

■ Annuals ■ Perennials

Results

CP

NDF

ADL

p-value (t-student) < 5%
Significant difference

Results

CF

ADF

Ash

p-value (t-student) > 5%
No significant difference

Evaluation of classification model and groups comparison

CP, CF, ADF, Ash

$P \geq 84\%$; $K \geq 0,6$

NDF & ADL

$P < 60\%$; $K \leq 0,4$

Classification of pasture species based on each biochemical compound content

n=114 species

Classification of pasture species based on their biochemical compound content

Classification of pasture species based on their biochemical compound content

Classification of forage plants (Chemical analysis)		
Group 1	Group 2	Group 3
<i>Stipa Tenacissima</i> <i>Lygeum Spartum</i>	<i>Peganum Harmala</i> <i>Artemisia Herba Halba</i> <i>Salsola Vermiculata</i> <i>Hordeum Murinum</i> <i>Anacyclus x Valentinus</i> <i>Astragalus Hamosus</i>	<i>Atriplex Nummularia</i> <i>Anabasis Aphylla</i> <i>Diploaxis Harra</i> <i>Vicia Monantha Retz</i> <i>Papaver Dubium</i> <i>Atractylis Serratuloides</i> <i>Malva Parviflora</i> <i>Plantago ovata</i> <i>Eruca Sativa</i> <i>Sonchus Asper</i> <i>Rumex Pulcher</i> <i>Avena Sterilis</i>

Classification of pasture species based on their biochemical compound content

Classification of forage plants (Chemical analysis)		
Group 1	Group 2	Group 3
<i>Stipa Tenacissima</i> <i>Lygeum Spartum</i>	<i>Peganum Harmala</i> <i>Artemisia Herba Halba</i> <i>Salsola Vermiculata</i> <i>Hordeum Murinum</i> <i>Anacyclus x Valentinus</i> <i>Astragalus Hamosus</i>	<i>Atriplex Nummularia</i> <i>Anabasis Aphylla</i> <i>Diploaxis Harra</i> <i>Vicia Monantha Retz</i> <i>Papaver Dubium</i> <i>Atractylis Serratuloides</i> <i>Malva Parviflora</i> <i>Plantago ovata</i> <i>Eruca Sativa</i> <i>Sonchus Asper</i> <i>Rumex Pulcher</i> <i>Avena Sterilis</i>

Precision = 95%
Kappa Coef = 0,91

Classification of forage plants (NIRS analysis)		
Group 1	Group 2	Group 3
<i>Stipa Tenacissima</i> <i>Lygeum Spartum</i>	<i>Peganum Harmala</i> <i>Artemisia Herba Halba</i> <i>Salsola Vermiculata</i> <i>Hordeum Murinum</i> <i>Anacyclus x Valentinus</i> <i>Astragalus Hamosus</i> <i>Diploaxis Harra</i>	<i>Atriplex Nummularia</i> <i>Anabasis Aphylla</i> <i>Vicia Monantha Retz</i> <i>Papaver Dubium</i> <i>Atractylis Serratuloides</i> <i>Malva Parviflora</i> <i>Plantago ovata</i> <i>Eruca Sativa</i> <i>Sonchus Asper</i> <i>Rumex Pulcher</i> <i>Avena Sterilis</i>

Classification of forage plants based on herders' perceptions

Classification of forage plants based on herders' perceptions		
Classe 1 : low or bad quality(<3)	Classe 2 : average quality(>=3 &<4)	Classe 3 : good quality(>=4)
<p><i>Peganum Harmala</i> <i>Anabasis Aphylla</i></p>	<p><i>Stipa Tenacissima</i> <i>Lygeum Spartum</i> <i>Papaver Dubium</i> <i>Atractylis Sarratuloides</i> <i>Anacyclus x Valentinus</i> <i>Eruca Sativa</i> <i>Avena Sterilis</i></p>	<p><i>Atriplex Nummularia</i> <i>Diploaxis Harra</i> <i>Hordeum Murinum</i> <i>Rumex Pulcher</i> <i>Artemisia Herba Halba</i> <i>Vicia Monantha Retz</i> <i>Malva Parviflora</i> <i>Plantago ovata</i> <i>Sonchus Asper</i> <i>Salsola Vermiculata</i> <i>Astragalus Hamosus</i></p>

Comparison of groups

Comparison of groupe

Precision = 35%
Kappa coef = -0,15

Reasons of difference

Conclusion

Floristic diversity
and biochemical
composition of
pasture species

Difference between
biochemical
composition and
farmers' perceptions

Reliability of the
chemical analysis
method

Bias in the NIRS
method

Improvement possibilities

- Expand the analytical database
- Measure nutrient content and their digestibility
- Conduct targeted analyses of secondary metabolites and antinutritional compounds.
- Further research into the interactions between the biochemical characteristics of plants and their palatability to animals.
- Develop and validate multi-criteria rating scales
- Develop practical techniques enabling farmers to assess forage quality in the field.

What's next ?

Scientific Publication

Estimation of Forage Balance in Sheep Production Systems in the Province of Rehamna. *Meryem Guedira, Abdelilah Araba, Soufiane El Aayadi*

Estimation du bilan fourrager dans les systèmes de production ovine dans la province de Rehamna

Meryem Guedira, Abdelilah Araba, Soufiane El Aayadi

► To cite this version:

Meryem Guedira, Abdelilah Araba, Soufiane El Aayadi. Estimation du bilan fourrager dans les systèmes de production ovine dans la province de Rehamna. 3R2024: 27èmes Rencontres autour des Recherches sur les Ruminants, Institut de l'élevage [I.DELE], INRAE, Dec 2024, Paris, France. hal-05109064

HAL Id: hal-05109064

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SEMINAIRE EN HYBRIDE
L'ÉLEVAGE DANS LES TERRES DE PARCOURS:
DÉFIS ET ALTERNATIVES DURABLES
Jeudi 30 novembre 2023
INRA - Centre régional de la recherche agronomique Oujda

PRIMA
IN THE NEXT 10 YEARS 2030
SURFLY

Estimation du bilan fourrager dans les systèmes de production ovine dans la province de Rehamna

M. GUEDIRA, C. EL BAKALI, A. ARABA et S. EL AAYADI
Institut Agronomique et Vétérinaire Hassan II, BP 6202, 10101, Rabat, Maroc

01 Introduction

Le changement climatique a des conséquences significatives sur la distribution des précipitations. Cette réalité impacte de manière particulièrement négative les régions arides du Maroc, entraînant les conséquences relatives sur divers aspects, dont la production animale. Cette dernière est particulièrement affectée par la production ovine, notamment les cultures fourragères et les terres de parcours. Dans des zones arides, à l'exemple de la zone de Rehamna, l'élevage ovin est envisagé comme un plan d'adaptation crucial pour les éleveurs locaux. Toutefois, répondre aux besoins alimentaires des animaux dans ce contexte exige une évaluation rigoureuse des ressources fourragères. Cette étude vise à caractériser les différents types de systèmes d'élevage ovin en fonction de leur mode d'élevage, d'évaluer la capacité à satisfaire les besoins alimentaires des ovins dans ce contexte de sécheresse récurrente. L'objectif est d'évaluer le bilan fourrager des systèmes de production ovine dans la province.

02 Matériel et méthodes

02.1 Collecte de données

Des enquêtes ont été menées dans la province de Rehamna, auprès de 30 éleveurs visant à caractériser les caractéristiques, les données et les systèmes d'élevage de la zone. Ensuite, une typologie a été établie pour identifier les différents types d'élevage présents.

02.2 Estimation du bilan fourrager

Pour estimer le bilan fourrager, la méthode recommandée par le FAO a été utilisée impliquant le calcul des besoins en LP spécifiques à chaque catégorie d'élevage présente au niveau de l'élevage, en vue de les comparer aux apports des différents réservoirs alimentaires caractérisés par le territoire aride. Ce calcul a été effectué par élevage type qui correspond à l'élevage le plus productif du cadre de la zone.

03 Résultats et discussions

03.1 Typologie des élevages

Les types d'élevage identifiés

Cette classification repose sur plusieurs variables, à la fois qualitatives et quantitatives, à savoir quatre types d'élevage :

- Type 1: élevage ovin basé sur l'élevage en stabulation et l'absence de disponibilité des ressources alimentaires.
- Type 2: élevage de type mixte, avec un accès à une quantité alimentaire du bétail bien maîtrisée.
- Type 3: l'activité principale des éleveurs est l'engraissement des ovins pour l'écou.
- Type 4: des grands éleveurs qui ne distinguent pas une quantité alimentaire minimale du bétail, mais ont un accès des parcours extensifs en matière de gestion des ressources alimentaires. La plupart de ces éleveurs sont des membres de l'ANCC.

03.2 Bilan fourrager

L'évaluation du bilan fourrager montre que le T1 et T3 se distinguent par les déficits les plus importants, soit 24% et 20% respectivement. En revanche, les types T2 et T4 présentent des déficits plus faibles, soit 2% et 1% respectivement.

Dans les types d'élevage identifiés, l'autonomie fourragère reste inférieure à 50%, ce qui signifie que la production de fourrage ne suffit pas à couvrir les besoins même dans la moitié des besoins alimentaires de chaque catégorie. Cependant, à la place d'irriguer et les parcours, il est une alternative fourragère de 46%.

Tableau 1: Caractéristiques relatives au bilan fourrager par type d'élevage

Types	T1 (%)	T2 (%)	T3 (%)	T4 (%)
Déficit	24	2	20	1
Autonomie fourragère	17,17	10,09	11,78	48,15
Part du pâturage	3,35	6,90	5,18	17,66
Contribution des éléments grossiers	20	36	18,17	45,58

04 Conclusion

Les types d'élevage ovins identifiés reposent d'une grande part des parcours moins productifs (50 LP/ha) et des terres cultivées non irriguées. Pour les éleveurs qui mélangent la culture alimentaire des bœufs, la culture et la terre sèche.

Cette situation de déficit fourrager chez l'ensemble des éleveurs aura des effets négatifs sur les performances zootechniques des animaux, notamment en ce qui concerne la fertilité, la production de viande et la croissance.

Il est donc recommandé la production des ovins, dans les régions arides, en suggérant une amélioration du système fourrager par l'introduction de cultures mixtes et intercalaires.

Cette étude a été financée dans le cadre du projet SURFLY et PMS-AGRO-INS.

Scientific Publication

Seasonal Variations in the Nutritional Value of Pasture Species in Morocco's Oriental Region: Forage Potential and Prospects for Livestock Farming

Classification of Sheep Forage Resources in the Steppes of Eastern Morocco Using Near-Infrared Spectroscopy (NIRS)

Taha Nour, Kaoutar Aboukhalid, Abdesselam Maâtougui, Hanane Khallouf, Said Otouya, Simon Taugourdeau, Lionel Julien, Soufiane El Aayadi

Classification of pastoral livestock systems and local ecological knowledge of forage resources in the steppe rangelands of Jerada Province (Eastern Morocco)

Kaoutar Aboukhalid, Taha Nour, Abdesselam Maâtougui, Hanane Khallouf, Said Otouya, Simon Taugourdeau, Lionel Julien, Soufiane El Aayadi

Work in progress

A Study of Farmers' Perceptions and a Comparison of the Nutritional Value of Agricultural Byproducts Using Conventional Methods and Near-Infrared Spectroscopy (NIRS) in the Oriental Region.

Academic and research development in the area of animal nutrition:

- Creating a reliable database of feed nutritional composition
- Developing In vivo and In vitro protocols to assess feed nutritional quality
- Developing reliable predictive model based on the NIRS method
- Exploring and studying feeding evaluation systems and adapting them to the Moroccan context

Thank you for your attention

Taha Nour.

Morocco (UIZ)

The 3^d Face to Face Meeting, May 12-13th, 2026, Mednine, Tunisia

The PRIMA Project PAS-AGRO-PAS :

“ The Making of Fragile Agro-ecosystems Productive, Adaptive and Sustainable: Multifunctional Agro-pastoralism ”

Bioprocess and Environment Team, LASIME Laboratory, Agadir Superior School of Technology, University Ibn Zohr, 80150 Agadir, Morocco

UIZ_Team

BRIEF PRESENTATION OF UIZ

Founded in 1989, University Ibn Zohr (UIZ-Avenzoar University) is the Morocco's largest university, with more than **150,000** students, covering **8 Cities** & **5 regions** of the Kingdom of Morocco :

- Souss Massa,
- Guelmim Oued Noun,
- Laayoune Sakia Lhamra,
- Dakhla Oued Eddahab
- Draa Tafilalt.

BRIEF PRESENTATION OF UIZ

- **Faculties and Schools**

Faculty of Sciences x2

Faculty of Letters and Human Sciences x2

Faculty of Law, Economics, and Social Sciences x2

Faculty of Medicine and Pharmacy x3

Polydisciplinary Faculty X2

National School of Applied Sciences X1

National School of Business and Management x2

Higher School of Technology x5

National Higher School of Data Science x1

- **Agadir Higher School of Technology**

- Provides technical and vocational education.
- Offers programs in areas like: Agro-food and environment, Information Technology, Business Management, and Industrial Maintenance.

AGADIR IN THE REGIONAL CONTEXT

With a **GDP of 64 MMDH**, the Souss Massa region accounts for more than **10.5%** of national added value and is the national leader in the primary sector.

LOCATION OF THE STUDY

Guelmim and Laâyoune regions, located in southern Morocco, represent key agropastoral zones for camel herding.

The **Arganeraie region**, located in the center of Morocco, is a semi-arid zone renowned for its endemic argan trees (*Argania spinosa*).

Characterization of the agro-pastoral systems in Morocco

Comparative Environmental Profile: *Arganeraie* vs. *Guelmim–Laâyoune Sakia El Hamra*

Parameter	Arganeraie Region	Guelmim–Laâyoune Sakia El Hamra
<p>~139,480 km² (Laâyoune) / ~10,783 km² (Guelmim Province)</p>		
<p>~271,344 (Laâyoune, 2023) / ~186,832 (Guelmim Province)</p>		
<p>Flat desert plains (Laâyoune) / Limestone plateaus (Guelmim)</p>		
<p>Arid to hyper-arid (67–120 mm/year), extreme temperatures</p>		
<p>Poor (yermosols), saline near coasts</p>		
<p>Desert shrubs (acacia), coastal halophytes, oasis palms</p>		
<p>Groundwater, polluted Sakia El Hamra River</p>		
<p>Nomadic pastoralism (camels), fishing, phosphate mining</p>		

Task 4.3.: Efficacy of the intervention strategies on animal productivity and carcass quality

Feed type	Main class	Protein level	Estimated usable energy
Cactus raquettes / pads	Succulent energetic feed	7% CP	≈ 1,580 kcal/kg DM
Banana leaves / aerial part	Green forage, moderate protein	10–17% CP depending on part	≈ 2,370 kcal/kg DM
Banana trunk / pseudostem	Succulent fibrous feed	3–5% CP	Low as-fed energy because it is mostly water
Hay / straw	Fibrous roughage	4–8% CP depending quality	≈ 1,600 kcal/kg DM
Dry palm tree leaves	Poor fibrous roughage	5% CP	≈ 1,340 kcal/kg DM
Date palm seeds / pits	Energetic fibrous concentrate	6% CP	≈ 2,750 kcal/kg DM
Barley grain	Energetic concentrate	12% CP	≈ 2,960 kcal/kg DM

WP4_Task 4.3. Strategies towards enhanced productivity and management of meat/dairy livestock

The planned work

Luzerne

Hay

Maize

Barley Grain

**Date palm's Seeds
(Phoenix dactylifera L)**

Cactus pads

Banana Plante

Dried palm leaves

WP4_ Task 4.5: Biometry, sensoring and animal activity

Biometric study

	The carcass in Cm				
Age	Weight (Kg)	Length	Total length	Height	Neck Length
3 days	1.83	28	40	32	13
48 days	6.48	40	57	41	19
90 days	8.68	46	70	47	13

WP4_ Task 4.5: Biometry, sensing and animal activity

The effect of humidity on weight in female goats

COMPARISON OF WEIGHT VERSUS TIME FOR FEMALE GOATS

■ Taddarte ■ Ait Melloul ■ Taroudante ■ Ait Milk ■ Tiznit ■ Essaouira

COMPARISON OF WEIGHT VERSUS TIME FOR MALE GOATS

■ Agadir ■ Ait Melloul ■ Taroudante ■ Ait Milk ■ Tiznit ■ Essaouira

WP5_Task 5.1: Multi-dimensional quality of the agro-pastoral food products

To evaluate the impact of the different agropastoral production system and their intervention strategies on the distinct dimensions of quality of meat and dairy production.

Enhancing the value of agri-food products derived from agropastoralism through the exploitation of its quality, safety, and typicity.

Fatty acid analysis and bacteriological analysis

WP5_Task 5.1: At least 3 banks of indigenous bacteriocinogenic and probiotic lactic acid bacteria from selected agro-pastoral products

Isolation of antagonistic Lactic Acid Bacteria

LAB Isolation

Antagonistic Activity Screening: Double Layer Method

Antagonistic Activity Screening: Well Diffusion Method

Phenotypic identification

- ❖ Gram staining
- ❖ Catalase test:
- ❖ Salt tolerance: Growth at 6.5% NaCl
- ❖ Alkaline tolerance: Growth at pH 9.6
- ❖ Thermotolerance: Growth at 45°C for 24 h
- ❖ Heat resistance: Survival at 60°C for 30 min

WP5_Task 5.3_Subtask 5.3.2: Incorporation of high value-added compounds into new products

WP5_Task 5.3: Development of innovative agro-pastoral food products

Camel Kefir

- **Development** : Production of kefir using camel milk from Agadir, Laâyoune, and Guelmim regions.
- **Probiotic Enrichment** : Incorporation of indigenous lactic acid bacteria (LAB) to enhance the probiotic content of the kefir and to control pathogens (*Listeria monocytogenes*, *Staphylococcus aureus*)
- **Nutritional Enhancement** : Improvement of nutritional properties by enriching the kefir with essential fatty acids and proteins, leveraging the unique characteristics of local milk.

Fabrication Process

WP5_Task 5.3: Development of innovative agro-pastoral food products

Artisanal Merguez Using Goat and Camel Meat

- **Development** : Development of merguez using camel and goat meat, reflecting the traditional livestock of the region.
- **Probiotic Enrichment** : Use of local spices and high-value biocompounds (e.g., polyphenol extracts from argan oil) to enhance flavor and antioxidant properties.
- **Nutritional Enhancement** : Utilization of local dietary fibers to reduce saturated fats in the merguez, aligning with regional dietary preferences.

Manufacturing Process

WP5_Task 5.3_Subtask 5.3.1: Extraction of high value-added compounds from crops or local agri-food residues

Zygophyllum Gaetulum

Marrubium vulgare L.

Matricaria Aurea

Punica granatum peels

Hydrodistillation extraction

polyphenols, dietary fibers, and plant-
Essential oils

Antioxidant, antimicrobial, and
nutritional properties

Communication activities

- Participation in the 1st Edition of the International Forum on Industry and Services in Souss-Massa, 5 & 6th May 25

WP8_Task 8.6: Divulagation materials for target audiences

pas-agro-pas

Socio-economic aspects of cooperatives: Amazigh girl matters

Doctoral Thesis Defenses

**Sanaa Benass December 20th,
2025**

**Kaoutar Boussif December 27th,
2025**

**Hamza Tami: Scheduled for
defense by the July 2026**

Published Articles

Title of the Article	Journal of publication	Authors	Date of Publication
<u>Effects of oregano and rosemary essential oils on the physicochemical, microbiological and organoleptic characteristics of fresh cheese</u>	Food and Humanity	<u>Sanaa Benassila</u> <u>Kaoutar Boussif</u> <u>Said El Hizazi</u> [...] <u>Fouad Achemchem</u>	May 2025
<u>Combined inhibitory action of oregano essential oil and autochthonous lactic acid bacteria against Listeria monocytogenes serovar 4b in Moroccan soft goat cheese under refrigeration</u>	Malaysian Journal of Microbiology	<u>Kaoutar Boussif</u> <u>Benassila, S.</u> <u>Safae Azzouz</u> [...] <u>Fouad Achemchem</u>	December 2025
<u>Lactic Acid Bacteria from Traditional Fermented Milk: Antimicrobial Potential Against Foodborne Pathogens</u>	Applied Microbiology	<u>Kaoutar Boussif</u> <u>Ahmed Elidrissi</u> <u>Abdelkhalek Elmoslih</u> [...] <u>Fouad Achemchem</u>	January 2026

Published Articles

Title of the Article	Journal of publication	Authors	Date of Publication
<p><u>Microbial contamination and antimicrobial resistance linked to genomic profiles in artisanal Merguez from Agadir, Morocco</u></p>	<p>Malaysian Journal of Microbiology</p>	<p><u>Ezzaky Youssef</u> <u>Mariam Zanzan</u> <u>Hamza Tami</u> [...] <u>Fouad Achemchem</u></p>	<p>May 2026</p>
<p><u>Antimicrobial Properties of Lactic Acid Bacteria Isolated from Moroccan Camel Meat for Natural Food Preservation (Conference Paper)</u></p>	<p>Foods 2025</p>	<p><u>Hamza Tami</u> <u>Ezzaky Youssef</u> <u>Mariam Zanzan</u> [...] <u>Fouad Achemchem</u></p>	<p>April 2026</p>
<p>2 Articles – Currently under Submission porocess</p>			
<p>3 Articles – Currently under peer review</p>			

Delivered Communications

Title of the Communication	Conference	Authors	Date of Communication
Cross-Species Microbiota: Comparative Isolation and Characterization of Lactic Acid Bacteria from Moroccan Goats' and Camels' Meat for Natural Food Preservation	1st edition of the International Congress of Industry, Biotechnology and Health (ICIBH-2025)	<u>Hamza Tami</u> , Youssef Ezzaky, Ahmed Elidrissi, Mariem Zanzan, Mohamed Amellal, and Fouad Achemlal.	October 14 and 15, 2025
Essential oil extraction using a supercritical CO ₂ extraction system and its impact on the antioxidant capacity of <i>Matricaria chamomil</i> L.	10th Edition of the International Research School "Biotechnological Innovations and Agroecological Resilience: Towards Sustainable and Inclusive Mediterranean Territories"	<u>Hamza Tami</u> , Jose Manuel Lorenzo, Roberto Bermúdez Piedra, Aurora Cittadini, Said Elhizazi, Fouad Achemchem ^{1*}	December 12–14, 2025, Agadir, Morocco
Isolation and Identification of Bacteriocinogenic Lactic Acid Bacteria from Camels' meat in the Souss Massa region	<u>The 6th International Electronic Conference on Foods</u>	<u>Hamza Tami</u> *, Youssef Ezzaky, Ahmed Elidrissi, Mariem Zanzan, Mohamed Amellal, and Fouad Achemchem	28-30 October, 2025
Functional and Antimicrobial Properties of Camel Milk-Based Kefir: Physicochemical Stability and Biopreservation Potential	<u>The 6th International Electronic Conference on Foods session Nutritional and Functional Foods</u>	Mohamed Wahbi, Mohamed Amellal, Imad Achlaih, Ahmed Elidrissi, Abir El-Araby, Fouad Achemchem	28-30 October, 2025
Development of a predictive model for the growth of <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i> in fresh goat cheese "Jben" under varying temperature conditions	<u>The 6th International Electronic Conference on Foods session Food Microbiology</u>	Kaoutar Boussif, Youssef Ezzaky, Mariem Zanzan, Antonio Valero, Fouad Achemchem	28-30 October, 2025
Improving the Microbiological Safety of Traditional Goat Merguez sausage from Morocco's Argan Region Using Indigenous Lactic Acid Bacteria	<u>The 6th International Electronic Conference on Foods session Food Quality and Safety</u>	Lobna Jilal, Hamza Tami, Youssef Ezzaky, Mariem Zanzan, Said El Hizazi, and Fouad Achemchem	28-30 October, 2025
Screening of Antagonistic Lactic Acid Bacteria Isolated	<u>The 6th International Electronic</u>	Mohamed Amellal, Youssef	28-30 October, 2025

المدرسة العليا للتكنولوجيا - أكادير
ÉCOLE SUPÉRIEURE DE TECHNOLOGIE D'AGADIR
ⵜⴰⴳⴷⵓⴷⴰ ⵜⴰⵏⵓⵔⴰⵏⵜ ⵜⴰⵙⴳⴷⵓⴷⴰⵜ - ⵏ ⵏⵓⵔⴰⵏⵜ .

PAS - AGRO - PAS

Thank you

For your attention !

The Making of Fragile Agro-ecosystems Productive, Adaptive and Sustainable:
Multifunctional Agro-pastoralism
PAS-Agro-PAS

3rd Face-to-Face Meeting PRIMA project PAS-AGRO-PAS
Wildlife & Livestock Laboratory (LEFS), Arid Zone Research
Institute (IRA), University of Gabes, Medenine, Tunisia
May 12-13, 2026

Halima EL HATMI, coordinator
Arid Land Institute (IRA)
Tunisia

PLAN

01 Update

02 Deliverables and planned works

03 Communication/Dissemination activities

04 Final Commitments

05 Conclusion

Updates on WP 5

WP N°	5		Lead beneficiary				CTC					
WP title	Valorisation of agro-pastoral food products											
Participant N°	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	
Short name	IPB	ECoE	APRI	SELMET	MoSAR	UNISS	IAV	UIZ	CTC	ITACyL	IRA	
PM/ participant	12,05	10	7	4,9	2,2	8	8	13,2	18	3	16	
Start month	6			End month				32				

Task	Valorisation of agro-pastoral food products	Lead
5.1	Multi-dimensional quality of the agro-pastoral food products	CTC
5.2	Typicity and differentiation of the agro-pastoral food products	SELMET
5.3	Development of innovative agro-pastoral food products	IRA
5.4	Shelf-life of agro-pastoral food products	IPB

Dairy Products

Task 5.1_Multi-dimensional quality of the agro-pastoral food products

Lead: **CTC**; Participants: IPB, ECoE, APRI, SELMET, MoSAR, UNISS, IAV, UIZ, ITACyL, IRA

Work carried out:

- Physicochemical Analysis**
 - pH, Acidity, Water Activity, Color
- Microbiological Analysis**
 - TBC, Yeasts & Molds, LAB, Coliforms
- Nutritional Analysis**
 - Fatty Acids, Proteins, Lactose
- Sensory Analysis**
 - Texture, Appearance, Taste & Flavor

Parameter	Milk	L'ben	Smen
pH	6.74±0.06	4.24±0.12	5.25±0.19
Acidity (°D)	23.5±2.02	75.9±3.83	13±0.07
Aw	0.961±0.022	0.96±0.01	0.619±0.01
Density	1.031±0.001	-	-
Viscosity (cP)	167.5±3.53	210±17.32	366.66±35.11
<i>L</i> *	72.48±0.49	71.91±1.38	60.43±0.03
<i>a</i> *	-2.52±0.042	-3.80±0.13	-10.24±0.03
<i>b</i> *	10.29±0.06	9,57±1,20	38.66±0.04

Lactometrics

Lactometrics

Lactometrics

General Information

Animal ID:

Date:

Region:

Breeder:

Biological and Genealogical Data

Species:

Breed:

Sex:

Birth Date:

Age (months):

Breeding and Management Systems

Breeding System:

Livestock System:

Diet:

Reproduction and Progeny

Kidding Date:

Litter Size:

Sex of Kids:

Morphometric Measurements

Body Length:

Pelvis Length:

Hip Width:

Physical Characteristics

Coat Color:

Dorsal Line:

Milk Production Indicators

Number of Milkings per Day:

Milk per Milking:

Milk per Day:

Milk Composition Analysis

pH:

Acidity:

Viscosity:

Milk related parameters

pH:

Iron:

Total Nitrogenous Matter:

Sodium:

Freezing Point:

Acidity:

Lactose:

Milk Solids:

Potassium:

Color and Appearance:

Viscosity:

Somatic Cell Count:

Fat:

Calcium:

Total Solids:

Microbial Load:

Total Proteins:

Zinc:

Mineral Matter:

Descriptive statistic data analysis: Lactometrics

Lactometrics

ANIMAL ID

REGION

BREEDER

SPECIES

BREED

SEX

AGE (MONTHS)

DIET

LITTER SIZE

WEANING WEIGHT

SCAPULO-ISCHIUM

WEANING AT BACK

HEIGHT AT SCAPULO

WEANING MILKING

MILK PERCENTAGE

TOTAL NITROGENOUS MATTER

MILK SOLIDS

POTASSIUM

CALCIUM

COBALT LOAD

FREEZING POINT

COLOR & APPEARANCE

Amount_of_milk_produced_per_day Statistics

COUNT

101

MEAN

2.44

MEDIAN

2.44

STANDARD DEVIATION

0.62

VARIANCE

0.38

COEFFICIENT OF VARIATION

25.30%

SKEWNESS

0.13

MINIMUM

1.01

MAXIMUM

4.13

25TH PERCENTILE

2.04

50TH PERCENTILE

2.44

75TH PERCENTILE

2.77

Visualization: Lactometrics

Select Category:

Milk Production

Select Attribute:

Milk per Day

Select Chart Type:

Histogram

Amount_of_milk_produced_per_day Distribution

Visualization: Rumetrics

Rumetrics

+ Add Animal

👁 View database

📊 Statistics

📈 Graphics

🔍 Help

📄 About

Select Category:

Physical Measurements

Select Attribute:

Length of body (cm)

Select Chart Type:

Box Plot

LengthOfBody Box Plot

Descriptive statistic data analysis: Lactometrics

Lactometrics

Coat_color Statistics

TOTAL COUNT OF OBSERVATIONS

101

NUMBER OF UNIQUE CATEGORIES

4

MOST FREQUENTLY OCCURRING
CATEGORY

spotted

COUNT OF MOST FREQUENT CATEGORY

32

PERCENTAGE OF MOST FREQUENT
CATEGORY

31.68%

SHANNON DIVERSITY INDEX (ENTROPY):

1.37

SIMPSON'S DIVERSITY INDEX (D):

0.26

Value Distribution

Value

Count

Percentage

Visualization: Lactometrics

Select Category:

Physical Characteristics

Select Attribute:

Coat Color

Select Chart Type:

Pie Chart

Coat_color Distribution

- black
- white
- spotted
- brown

Meat Products

Task 5.1_Multi-dimensional quality of the agro-pastoral food products

Lead: **CTC**; Participants: IPB, ECoE, APRI, SELMET, MoSAR, UNISS, IAV, UIZ, ITACyL, IRA

Indigenous LAB will be isolated from some agro-pastoral food products. (collaboration with IUZ)

80 strains

14 camel milk

31 ewe milk

35 goat milk

Pré-sélection	Technologique	Antimicrobienne
Coloration de Gram	Acidification mesure de la différence de pH: Δ pH 24 h et Δ pH 48 h	Pourcentage d'inhibition par mesure de do avant et après 24 h (méthode microplaques): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>B.Cereus</i> • <i>E.Coli</i> • <i>S.Typhimurium</i> • <i>S.aureus</i>
Test Catalase	Production des exopolysaccharides	
Fermentation du lactose	Activité lipolytique	
	Activité protéolytique	
	Activité antioxydant : DPPH et ABTS	

Conditions for bacterial isolation				Screening tests			
Codes	Type of milk	temps de prelevement	Batch date	Isolation medium	Gram staining	Catalase test	Lactose fermentation
AS1	Brebis	T16		MRS	+	-	+
AS2	Brebis	T12		MRS	+	-	+
AS3	Brebis	T20		MRS	+	-	+
AS4	Brebis	T12		MRS	+	-	+
AS5	Brebis	T12		MRS	+	-	+
AS6	Brebis	T20		MRS	+	-	+
AS7	Brebis	T16		MRS	+	-	+
AS8	Brebis	T16		MRS	+	-	+
AS9	Brebis		15/05/2024	MRS	+	-	+
AS10	Brebis		15/05/2024	MRS	+	-	+
AS11	Brebis		15/05/2024	MRS	+	-	+
AS12	chamelle		09/01/2025	MRS	+	-	+
AS13	chamelle		09/01/2025	MRS	+	-	+
AS14	chamelle		09/01/2025	MRS	+	-	+
AS15	chamelle		09/01/2025	MRS	+	-	+
AS16	chamelle		09/01/2025	MRS	+	-	+
AS17	chamelle	T12	05/04/2024	MRS	+	-	+
AS18	chamelle	T24	05/04/2024	MRS	+	-	+
AS19	chamelle	T12	05/04/2024	MRS	+	-	+
AS20	chamelle	T12	05/04/2024	MRS	+	-	+
AS21	chamelle	T12	05/04/2024	MRS	+	-	+
AS22	chamelle	T12	05/04/2024	MRS	+	-	+
AS23	chevre			MRS	+	-	+
AS24	chevre			MRS	+	-	+
AS25	chevre			MRS	+	-	+
AS26	chevre			MRS	+	-	+
AS27	chevre			MRS	+	-	+

Task 5.2_Typicity and differentiation of the agro-pastoral food products

Lead: **SELMET**; Participants: IPB, ECoE, APRI, SELMET, MoSAR, UNISS, IAV, UIZ, ITACyL, IRA

Geographic factors

Cultural factors

Climatic factors

Task 5.3_Development of innovant agro-pastoral foods

Lead: **IRA**; Participants_UIZ, CTC, UNISS, ITACyL

Subtask 5.3.1: Extraction of high value-added compounds from crop or local agri-food residues
Collaboration with CTC

Innovative extraction process

Optimized
Extraction

High Nutritional
Compounds

Analysis & Characterization

Total Polyphenols

Antioxidant Properties

Subtask 5.3.2: Incorporation of high value-added compounds into new products:

- Antimicrobial Efficacy of Olive Leaf Extract in Soft Cheese
- Fermented camel milk fortified with pomegranate syrup and peel powder
- Fermented goat milk butter fortified with fig/date powder

Olive Leaf Extract Preparation Process

Source Material

- Sredki variety olive leaves
- Origin: Siliana Sud, Tunisia

Extraction Protocol

- Dried at 60°C to constant weight
- Aqueous extraction: 1:10 ratio, 55°C, 30 min, 200 rpm

Phenolic Content & Antioxidant Activity:

- TPC
- DPPH
- ABTS

Antimicrobial Activity against *L. monocytogenes* by Broth microdilution assay

- Serial dilutions: 200 to 6.25 mg/mL
- MTT indicator for MIC
- Agar plating for MBC

Time-Dependent Anti-Listeria Effect

- Concentrations: ½×MIC, 1×MIC, 2×MIC, 4×MIC
- BHI broth in microtiter plates
- 1:1 ratio with bacterial suspension
- OD600 measured every 2h for 24h

Soft Cheese Challenge Test

Food Matrix Application

Control Group (SF+LM)

- Inoculated cheese
- No extract added

Test Group (SF+OLE+LM)

- Cheese with OLE supplementation
- Prior to inoculation
- **Biointervention treatment**

Inoculation

Listeria monocytogenes ATCC
19117

$\sim 10^5$
CFU/g inoculation level

Storage and Microbial Analysis

Storage Condition: 4°C to simulate post-processing contamination

Study Duration: 7 Days

Mathematical Model Used: Baranyi-Roberts Model (no lag phase)

Main Results

Time-Dependent Anti-Listeria Effect

- MBC/MIC = 8 indicates bacteriostatic activity at sub-MIC concentrations and bactericidal at higher concentrations.
- Dose-dependent inhibition
- 4×MIC shows complete suppression
- 2×MIC shows significant delay

Main Results

L. monocytogenes Behavior in Cheese+ OLE

Key Findings:

- OLE : Decline to 4.83 log CFU/g

Baranyi-Roberts Model (No Lag Phase)

Baranyi Roberts (no lag)						
Cheese samples	N_0 (log CFU/g)	Maximum growth rate (h^{-1})	N_f (log CFU/g)	Average of total reduction (log CFU/g)	RMSE	R^2
SF+LM	5.4	-0.04	5.24	0.15	0.014	0.94
SF+OLE+LM	5.42	-0.16	4.82	0.6	0.03	0.98

- All samples show negative growth rates, indicating bacterial decline throughout storage.
- OLE: 0.6 (log CFU/g) Total reduction after 7 days

Main Results

composition	CTRL	B 4	B 8	B 12
pH	4,363±0,004	4,523±0,017	4,596±0,004	4,623±0,011
Dry Matter (g/100g)	57,4	57,9	58,4	61,6
Protein (g/100g)	2,842±0,005	3,797±0,04	4,582±0,21	5,584±0,13
Ash (g/100 g)	0,614±0,11	0,6905±0,004	0,7315±0,01	0,974±0,01
Na	24,61±2,15	21,67±2,63	29,59±0,65	26,21±2,23
k	54,91±16	85,45±2,35	149,63±2,75	156,35±12,19
Ca	37,48±5,02	40,89±3,59	60,34±8,52	56,54±0,04
Mg	6,31±0,73	8,48±0,4	13,26±1,48	14,65±0,7
Cu	0,13±0,05	0,14±0,04	0,18±0,06	0,19±0,02
Zn	0,08±0,32	0,09±0,03	0,11±0,01	0,16±0
Fe	00,53±0,11	00,92±0,03	01,33±0,1	01,13±0,3
aw	0.972±0.001	0.965±0.001	0.959±0.000 4	0.966±0.0006
L*	61,28±	60,8±0.01	54,375±0.12 5	53,17±0.06
a *	-1,84±	0,69±0.01	1,545±0.03	2,44±0.01
b *	4,19±	13,03±0.02	14,71±0.02	16,06±0.02
Acid Value/ Acidity Index	2,83	3,981	5,326	6,352
FFA (% of oleic acid)	1,99	2,806	3,75	4,47
Peroxide Value (meqO ₂ /kg)	2,2	1,8	1,4	0,6
TBA (mg MDA/kg)	0,091±0,001	0,089±0,006	0,096±0,018	0,110±0,005

Main Results

Variation of peroxy value

Main Results

Formulation de la base lactée avec des différentes doses

	PtType	Blocks	EG (%)	SG (%)	LC (%)
1	-1	1	0,125	3	96,875
2	1	1	0	0	100
3	-1	1	0,375	9	90,625
4	1	1	0,5	12	87,5
5	-1	1	0,375	3	96,625
6	-1	1	0,125	9	90,875
7	0	1	0,25	6	93,75
8	1	1	0,5	0	99,5
9	1	1	0	12	88

Diférente
dose
expérimenté

Simplex Design Plot in Amounts

Mixture Contour Plot of viscosity (component amounts)

Contour Plot of Taste; Overall acceptability; viscosity (component amounts)

Mixture Contour Plot of Overall acceptability (component amounts)

Optimisation sensorielle d'une base lactée fermentée

la formulation optimale : 9% de sirop de grenade + 0,5% de poudre d'écorce, offrant la meilleure acceptabilité .

Main Results

Caractérisation physico-chimique au cours de la conservation à 4 °C.

		Période de conservation à 4°C (jours)					
		1	7	14	21	28	35
pH	TM	4,66	4,63	4,64	4,68	4,59	4,59
	OP	4,6	4,82	4,83	4,795	4,596	4,447
Acidité	TM	60	51	57	54	45	48
	OP	63	39	60	57	72	78

Evolution de la flore mésophile totale au cours du stockage à 4°C.

		Flore mésophile totale (10 ⁶ UFC/ml)					
		Durée de stockage (jours)					
		1	7	14	21	28	35
TM		0,889	1,272	1,422	1,591	25086,667	35593,333
OP		1,548	1,438	0,979	1,422	87,1	24,297

Evolution de la flore bactérienne lactique

		Bactéries lactiques (10 ⁶ UFC/ml)					
		Durée de stockage (jours)					
		1	7	14	21	28	35
TM		21,499	101,309	242,674	241,176	10146,125	15834,5
OP		73,969	112,061	141,375	242,675	1288	1919,875

Evolution de la charge en levures et moisissures au cours du stockage à 4°C

		Levures et moisissures (10 ⁶ UFC/ml)					
		Durée de stockage (jours)					
		1	7	14	21	28	35
TM		0,805	301,517	339,166	350,55	0	0
OP		0,505	339,167	235,633	339,167	3273,167	0

Delivrables & planed work

D5.1: Quality and safety of the agro-pastoral products from living labs pre-intervention (Planned submission: 2026)

D5.2 : At least 3 banks of indigenous bacteriocinogenic and probiotic lactic acid bacteria from selected agro pastoral products (Planned submission : 2027)

D5.3 : Quality of newly developed functional food products (Planned submission: 2027)

D5.4 : Shelf-life predictive models of current agro-pastoral food products and newly-developed functional food products (In progress)

D5.5 : Quality and safety of the agro-pastoral products from living labs post-intervention (not involved)

D5.6 : Notebooks of quality standards for foods containing quality/typicity attributes (not involved)

Planned Work

- Fermented buttermilk fortified with *Opuntia deltinii* fruit powder
- Incorporation of palm by-product and/or olive oil regarding their potent antioxidant activity and dietary fiber composition in dry-fermented Merguez sausage
- Characterization of bacterial communities of agro-pastoral dairy products

Involved pearson

04
students
(Master)

02 PhD
students

03 Post-
Doc
positions:

CASE STUDIES: MAIN ISSUES

We focus on Tunisian arid zones as a hot spot for this study. These zones are characterized by:

- Drought, climate change and variability
- Vulnerable natural resources and risks of desertification
- Vulnerability of production systems and livelihoods (productivity, income instability,)
- Weak and instable economic growth, especially in rural areas, increase of unemployment rate, rural marginalization and depopulation
- Weak institutional and multi-stakeholders governance and coordination

CASE STUDIES: MAIN ISSUES

→ The main challenge here is to **enhance resilience and decrease vulnerability** of production systems and livelihoods in these regions

- 1) improving the economic performance of the rural regions,
- 2) using and management of the natural resources in a more sustainable, efficient and integrated manner,
- 3) creating new opportunities, new products, new markets, new institutions, new jobs, be more innovative, productive and competitive,
- 4) better effectiveness of the role and functioning of the local institutions, policy makers, farmers, local actors, research, etc., around social innovations

Characterisation of the agropastoral systems in Tunisia : Béni Khédache and Sidi Makhlouf

Two different regions of southern Tunisia (relief, landscapes, resources, socio-economic aspects, access to resources, agropastoral activities and practices, uses, development actions, etc.)

Agropastoral system of camel production in Sidi Makhlof

Goat breed system in Beni-kheddache

In these two systems:

- Animal feeding is Based on forage systems close to the farm
- Dairy production is a significant source of income of farmers.
- Goats and camels products such as milk are some of the important factors contributing to the economy of farmers living in these regions.

To implement the proposed strategies to improve these agropastoral systems and value chains, the project proposes to work within the framework of a living lab

→ Network, platform, partnership, multi-actor arena grouped to co-create knowledge and test alternative solutions to these case study issues.

→ It is intended to facilitate the suggested innovation process and research action, improve communication and participation in solving the problems of the studied territories (local resources valorization, livelihood resilience, local development).

**FRAMEWORK OF PASAGROPAS
MULTISTAKEHOLDER PLATFORM: 9 GROUPS
& 12 REPRESENTATIVES**

Agriculture development services

Delegation

معهد المناطق القاحلة (IRA)

جامعة قابس (Gabes university: academics & students, ISBAM)

الشركة التعاونية زاد الخير سيدي مخلوف (Mutual agricultural service company)

وكالة النهوض بالاستثمارات الفلاحية (Agency for the Promotion of Agricultural Investments)

اتحاد الفلاحين (Farmers union)

المزارعين (Farmers, breeders)

مؤسسات صغرى و متوسطة (Private: SME)

Technological hub

IRA incubator

جمعية الشباب الزموري (Youth association)

WP2, WP6 and WP8
Ongoing Activities, Preliminary Results
and Planned Work

Activities carried out (WP2)

1) Organization of the first awareness-raising and information multi-stakeholders workshop (January 25, 2024), Attended by around 40 stakeholders :

- Presentation of the PAS-AGRO-PAS project objectives, approaches and methods, activities and expected results
- Deepening the understanding of living laboratories for participatory innovation
- Present and discuss some achievements of development programs
- Evaluate reactions, acceptance rate and readiness for collaboration, and coming up with practical proposals to activate the living laboratory, participation and networking

(Deliverable : minutes of the workshop distributed to the involved key stakeholders)

Workshop

The poster features logos at the top for the Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research, the Ministry of Agriculture, and the PRIMA program. The main title is "First project workshop PAS-AGRO-PAS". Below this, the English text reads "The Making of Fragile Agro-ecosystems Productive, Adaptive and Sustainable: Multifunctional Agro-pastoralism". The Arabic text translates this as "جعل النظم الإيكولوجية الزراعية المشقة منتجة وقادرة على التكيف والاستدامة". The date is "JANUARY 25th, 2024" and the location is "Institut des Régions Arides, Médenine - Tunisia". The Arabic text also states "2024 جانفي 25، معهد المناطق القاحلة، مدين - تونس". The poster includes images of a camel, sheep, and a desert landscape. Logos for ISBAM, ANR, and IRECSA are at the bottom.

Ministère de l'Enseignement Supérieur, de la Recherche Scientifique

PRIMA

The PRIMA programme is supported by the Federal and Regional Governments of the participating countries for Research and Innovation

وزارة الزراعة والغذاء والتنمية الريعية
Ministère de l'Agriculture, des Ressources Halieutiques et de la Pêche

First project workshop

PAS-AGRO-PAS

The Making of Fragile Agro-ecosystems Productive, Adaptive and Sustainable: Multifunctional Agro-pastoralism

جعل النظم الإيكولوجية الزراعية المشقة منتجة وقادرة على التكيف والاستدامة

JANUARY 25th, 2024
Institut des Régions Arides,
Médenine - Tunisia

2024 جانفي 25،
معهد المناطق القاحلة،
مدين - تونس

PAS-AGRO-PAS

ISBAM

ANR

IRECSA

2) Characterization of the current context of agropastoral systems (action 1) and description of the most influential external drivers (environmental, social, economic, political, technological, legal) and their implications in the camel milk chain and Goat breed in Beni-kheddache)

(Deliverable : excel file : case study characterisation)

3) Data collection : Field surveys carried out in Béni Khédache (14-02-2024) and Sidi Makhlouf (21-02-2024), with 20 farmers (10 in BK and 10 in SM):

- Description of the farm, herd management, animal products and marketing, market, agropastoral policies, operators and operations of the camel milk value chain, livelihoods of agropastoralists, income, abandonment and exodus, transfer of know-how, contribution of gender to the local economy, data for cost-benefit analysis, etc.)
- The data was entered on an Excel file and prepared for statistical and socioeconomic analyses

4) SWOT analyses were carried out (February 2025) about the states of agropastoral systems and suggestion of tailor-made and targeted strategies (action 3) (work done with the main stakeholders within focus group discussions organized at the agriculture services in BK and SM)

(Deliverable : SWOT analysis report

WP6 ACTIVITIES

WORK CARRIED OUT

- Interviews with stakeholders and operators in the agropastoral value chain (mainly concerning the development of camel and goat milk, but also the development of agricultural by-products (April 2025).

WORK IN PROGRESS

- Initial economic analyses (income, expenses, profitability, etc.) and the profit margin of value chain operators.
- Economic profitability study of the different operations in the camel and goat milk value chains + operators' profit margins
- Evaluation of income, livelihoods, abandonment and exodus phenomenon, transfer of know-how, contribution of gender to the local economy

PLANNED WORK

- "Cost-Benefit" analysis of the valorization of agropastoral by-products
- Suggestion of policy guidelines for improving the value chain

→ Still waiting for analysis protocols, approaches and methods from SELMET partner

WP8 ACTIVITIES

WORK CARRIED OUT

- Awareness and information workshop for involved stakeholders in the agropastoral sector in Tunisia (organized at IRA (25-01-2024))
- Field visit, Béni Khédache area (14-02-2024) (with operators and operations of the agropastoral value chain)
- Field visit, Sidi Makhlouf area (21-02-2024) (with operators and operations of the agropastoral value chain)
- May-September 2025: Trainings for rural women in Béni Khédache and Sidi Makhlouf (on hygienic methods of milk collection and conservation, innovative milk processing methods and products)

PAS-AGRO-PAS

Update, work towards deliverables, communication/dissemination activities

Annual Meeting – May 12 & 13, 2026

PAS - AGRO - PAS

The PRIMA programme is supported and funded under Horizon 2020, the Framework European Union's Programme for Research and Innovation

Partner identification

- **Partner acronym and institution:** UMR SELMET, INRAE (France)
- **Contact person / PI:** Amandine Lurette
- **Main work packages and tasks involving the partner**
 - WP2 leader and task leader of 2.1, 2.2, 2.4 & 2.5 (with UMR Mosar)
 - Task leader of 4.6 & 5.2
 - Activities carrying out in others WPs
- **Main deliverables involving the partner**
 - D2.1: Common conceptual model of agro-pastoral production systems in interaction with their surrounding environment
 - D2.4: Transversal analysis of farms characterization (agro-pastoral system and SWOT) to identify common patterns and prototypes of strategy for the studied agro-pastoral farming systems
 - D4.5: Predictive models for enhanced management of local breeds
 - D5.6: Notebooks of quality standards for foods containing quality/typicity attributes

INRAE

Update

- **Work completed since the previous consortium meeting**
 - D2.4: Transversal analysis of farms characterization (agro-pastoral system and SWOT) to identify common patterns and prototypes of strategy for the studied agro-pastoral farming systems (September 2025)
 - Master's Thesis : Characterization of the diversity of agro-pastoral systems in the Aude region (2026, february)
- **Main scientific, technical or operational results**
- **Activities completed in the living labs, field work, laboratory work, modelling, platform development or stakeholder engagement**
 - Research Engineer contract : Exploring Climate Change Adaptation Levers at Territorial Scales and the Role of Pastoralism: Application to the Ségala region in Occitanie (2027, April))
 - Master's Thesis : Characterization of functional diversity within dairy ewe flocks in the Roquefort region, and its relationship to livestock management practices (2026, September)

Work towards deliverables

- **Deliverables already completed**
 - D2.1: Common conceptual model of agro-pastoral production systems in interaction with their surrounding environment (November 2024)
 - D2.4: Transversal analysis of farms characterization (agro-pastoral system and SWOT) to identify common patterns and prototypes of strategy for the studied agro-pastoral farming systems (October 2025)
- **Deliverables still pending**
 - D4.5: Predictive models for enhanced management of local breeds
 - D5.6: Notebooks of quality standards for foods containing quality/typicity attributes
- **Remaining work until project closure**
 - D4.5: Predictive models for enhanced management of local breeds
 - Simulations to be conducted (using the developed model) based on different herd configurations and climatic shock in dairy sheep systems.
 - D5.6: Notebooks of quality standards for foods containing quality/typicity attributes
 - How the quality, in term of typicity of the agro-pastoral products, is constructed ? We know that it is based on origin, on farmer's management including feeding system, on processing know-how, etc. Moreover, it is a compromise combining "uniqueness" and diversity of products and practices.
 - We proposed a template which that be filled with each case

Communication/dissemination activities

○ Papers

- Dedieu et al., 2026. Research on pastoralism in France: state of knowledge and current issues. Cahiers Agricultures, 2026, 35, pp.4. [10.1051/cagri/2025040](https://doi.org/10.1051/cagri/2025040) - **WP7**
- Deschamps & Jouven, 2026. How is decision-making about grazing management influenced by reliance on rangelands at farm level? Insights from small ruminant farms in French Mediterranean areas. Pastoralism: Research, Policy and Practice (In press) - **WP3**
- Drevon et al., 2024. How does a superior quality signe guarantee the quality of lamb meat? The Label Rouge case. Animal, 18(10), 101312. – **WP5**
- Drevon et al., 20XX. Meat quality and multifunctionality of agropastoral livestock systems: past and present insights from a French native grassland-based beef production. The Rangeland Journal (submitted) – **WP5**
- Le Goff et al., 20XX. Exploration of a mechanistic and dynamic model to represent functional diversity in dairy goat, Animal Open Space (submitted) – **WP4**

Communication/dissemination activities

○ Conferences

- Deschamps & Jouven, 2025. How do farmers manage to take best advantage of semi-natural and wooded pastures in Mediterranean agro-silvo-pastoral systems? In Joint Seminar FAO–CIHEAM – Agrosilvopastoral Futures: Bridging Tradition with Innovation in Mediterranean and Mountain Pastures, Kuşadası District, Aydın Province, Turkey, 9–11 April 2025. – **WP3**
- Deschamps et al., 2026. Caractériser et structurer la diversité fonctionnelle des ressources pastorales : vers un outil d'aide à la décision pour la gestion du pâturage sur parcours. Oral presentation presented at Rencontres Recherches Ruminants, 2–3 December 2026. – **WP3**
- Deschamps et al., 2026. Integrating grazing behaviour and local knowledge to classify Mediterranean rangeland resources. Oral communication presented at the European Grassland Federation Meeting, Évora, Portugal, 12–16 April 2026. – **WP3**
- Berlingieri-Damestoy et al., 2026. Exploration de leviers d'adaptation face au changement climatique des systèmes agropastoraux à l'échelle des fermes et du territoire : l'exemple du Ségala, un territoire d'Occitanie, Séminaire « pastoralismes: regards croisés sur l'avenir, Mars 2026, Montpellier, France – **WP7**
- Le Goff et al., 2026. Rôle de la diversité animale au sein du troupeau pour l'adaptation des systèmes d'élevage agropastoraux au changement climatique, Séminaire « pastoralismes: regards croisés sur l'avenir, Mars 2026, Montpellier, France – **WP4**
- Lauvie et al., 2024. Contribution de l'animal à la résilience globale des systèmes : quels enseignements peut-on tirer des systèmes à composante pastorale ?. 3R 2024, Institut de l'Elevage - INRAE, Dec 2024, Paris, France. pp.409-413. [hal-04912412](https://hal.inrae.fr/hal-04912412) – **WP4**
- Stark et al., 2026. Diversité des systèmes agropastoraux du pourtour méditerranéen : une analyse comparative, Séminaire « pastoralismes: regards croisés sur l'avenir, Mars 2026, Montpellier, France – **WP2**
- Nozières-Petit et al., 2026. Agropastoral farming systems face to climate change, which flexibility and rigidity? The case of Picodon PDO production in south-east of France, POLLEN Conference 2026, Barcelona June 29 - July 3, 2026 – **WP6**
- Drevon et al., 2025. Pastoral resources and quality signs: from construction to erosion? Some cases in the South-East of France. XII International Rangeland Congress, Working together for our global rangelands future, June 2025, Adelaide, SA, Australie – **WP5**

Communication/dissemination activities

○ Posters

- Le Goff et al., 2025. The role of herd functional diversity on Mediterranean agropastoral dairy systems' performance in a changing climate. 76. Annual Meeting of the EAAP, Aug 2025, Innsbruck, Austria. Wageningen Academic Publishers, 39, pp.409 hal-05346380 – **WP4**
- Stark et al., 2026. PAS-AGRO-PAS : Vers des systèmes agropastoraux méditerranéens multi-performants, résilients et durables, Séminaire « pastoralismes: regards croisés sur l'avenir, Mars 2026, Montpellier, France. – **WP2**

○ Dissemination outputs

- Seminar "Pastoralism: Perspectives for the Future" (<https://avenir-pasto.seminaire.inrae.fr/>) + social media com. 200 participants - **WP8**
- Transhumance 360 (<https://transhumances360.org/en/>) a virtual reality exhibition in the heart of pastoral mobility across the world (+ social media com.) - **WP8**

○ Activities still planned before project closure

- A few conferences (Pollen in Barcelona, EAAP Regional Meeting in Sassari, Rencontres Recherches Ruminants in Paris, Sommet de l'Elevage in Clermont-Ferrand, EAAP in Hambourg...)
- Finalizing publications

Final commitments

- **What the partner will deliver**
 - D4.5: Predictive models for enhanced management of local breeds
 - D5.6: Notebooks of quality standards for foods containing quality/typicity attributes
- **Responsible person**
 - D4.5: A. Lurette
 - D5.6: M.-O. Nozières-Petit
- **Supporting partners, if applicable**
 - Case study coordinators to complete D5.6 proposal made by M.-O. Nozières-Petit (Several reminders sent)
- **Deadline**
 - D4.5: February 2027
 - D5.6: Submit materials by the end of June (only 2 case studies at this stage) – analysis in the fall
- **Risks or support needed from the consortium**
 - -> Lack on transversality within the WPs and between the WPs
 - Risk of linear reporting to the funder (by partner), as already highlighted in the mid-term report

PAS-AGRO-PAS

Update, work towards deliverables, communication/dissemination activities

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PAS - AGRO - PAS

Institut des Régions Arides

Third meeting PAS-AGRO-PAS project
(12-13 May 2026)

WP5: Valorisation of agro-pastoral food products

Ursula Gonzales-Barron and Vasco Cadavez
Centro de Investigação de Montanha (CIMO), IPB

Objective of WP5

- The quality and safety of typical meat, milk and dairy products will be evaluated to ensure the exploitation of the “typicity” features of agro-pastoral food products.
- New functional foods will be developed to target new markets and consumers in terms of healthiness, convenience, ease of preparation and taste acceptability.
- The shelf-life of traditional and innovative products will be provided.

1. Quality and safety of typical agro-pastoral products

1. Quality and safety of typical agro-pastoral products

- (A) Lactic acid bacteria (LAB) isolated from alheira, chorizo and cheese have been characterised phenotypically and genotypically
 - Phenotypically: Acidification capacity; proteolytic activity; lipolytic activity; antimicrobial activity against *Salmonella*, *L. monocytogenes* and *S. aureus* (inhibition diameter), lactic acid production
 - Genotypically: WGS

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 - Genotypically: WGS

1. Quality and safety of typical agro-pastoral products

- Alheira LABs: Relationship between pH drop parameters and LAC production genes

1. Quality and safety of typical agro-pastoral products

- (B) Assuring the safety of traditional goat's milk cheese by two intervention strategies

- Adding a strain of LAB (proven to have anlisterial effects: *Leuconostoc mesenteroides*)
- Acidifying the milk

Figure 4. Effect of specific lactic acid bacteria (LAB) strains on the optimum growth rate (1/day; left) and maximum concentration of *L. monocytogenes* (log CFU/g; right) in heat-treated reconstituted milk adjusted at different pH, as estimated by the pH-driven dynamic model. Bars represent \pm standard error of the growth rate estimate.

1. Quality and safety of typical agro-pastoral products

- (B) Assuring the safety of traditional goat's milk cheese by two intervention strategies
 - Adding a strain of LAB (proven to have anlisterial effects: *Leuconostoc mesenteroides*)
 - Acidifying the milk

Figure 2. Comparison of the optimum growth rates of *L. monocytogenes* in reconstituted milk model medium and goat's pasteurized milk cheese, obtained in monoculture (left) and in coculture with *Leuconostoc mesenteroides* (right). Bars represent ± standard error of the estimate.

1. Quality and safety of typical agro-pastoral products

- (B) Assuring the safety of traditional goat's milk cheese by two intervention strategies
 - Model validation

Figure 6. First Validation: Determination of the conversion factor (Cf) for estimating the optimum growth rate of *L. monocytogenes* (LM) in goat's milk cheese from the optimum growth rate in reconstituted milk model medium. Horizontal and vertical bars represent \pm standard error of the optimum growth rate estimates. Mean and standard error of Cf are displayed on the top. The linear regression without intercept produced a residual standard error of 0.04263 on 5 degrees of freedom; and an adjusted R^2 of 0.9987. Type of culture (no LAB added, coculture with *L. mesenteroides*) was non-significant at $p = 0.32$.

2. Typicity and differentiation of agropastoral food products

2. Typicity and differentiation of agropastoral food products

- (A) Quality benchmarking of Portuguese chouriço produced in the North of Portugal

2. Typicity and differentiation of agropastoral food products

- **Cluster 1:** more industrialized chouriças, with some type of starter culture, as evidenced by its high LAB counts, faster pH drop retaining moisture
- **Cluster 2:** represent rather traditionally prepared chouriças. The very low water content (a_w and moisture) is typical of long-cured artisanal sausages, with intermediate LAB counts
- **Cluster 3:** appears to illustrate the most industrialized chouriças, as seen by low pH and high moisture/ a_w , together with high ash, low LAB counts, and low *S. aureus*/*Clostridium* spp. counts.

3. Development of innovative agropastoral food products

Slice at Fermentation Temperature = 20

3. Development of innovative agropastoral food products

- (A) Development of goat's milk kefir
 - To optimize the production parameters for goat's milk kefir, focusing on incubation time, temperature, and grain/milk ratio to achieve standard technological and microbiological qualities of kefir

Slice at Ratio = 1

Slice at FermentationTemperature = 20

Slice at FermentationTemperature = 20

3. Development of innovative agropastoral food products

- (A) Development of goat's milk kefir
 - Compare two types of kefir (plain and flavored) in terms of consumer preference.

3. Development of innovative agropastoral food products

● (B) Development of goat's pasteurised cheese fermented with:

- *Selected LAB cocktail*
- *L. mesenteroides* only
- *Kefir grains*
- Microbial stability, textural properties, sensory analysis

3. Development of innovative agropastoral food products

● (B) Development of goat's pasteurised cheese fermented with:

- *Selected LAB cocktail*
- *L. mesenteroides only*
- *Kefir grains*
- Microbial stability, textural properties, sensory analysis

3. Development of innovative agropastoral food products

- (C) Valorization of goat's milk whey as raw material in the production of

- Whey kefir
- Optimization

3. Development of innovative agropastoral food products

- (C) Valorization of goat's milk whey as raw material in the production of
 - However, in terms in sensory analysis whey kefir did not have high acceptability
 - Replace with goat's milk
 - Replace with powder milk

4. Shelf life of agropastoral food products

4. Shelf life of agropastoral food products

- (A) Shelf life of whey kefir with added powder milk

4. Shelf life of agropastoral food products

(B) Shelf life of goat's pasteurized milk cheese produced with LAB cocktail and kefir

(C) Shelf life of goat's milk kefir (plain and flavoured)

Dissemination

Systematic Review

A Meta-Analysis on the In Vitro Antagonistic Effects of Lactic Acid Bacteria from Dairy Products on Foodborne Pathogens

Yara Loforte ^{1,2}
and Ursula Gonzales-Barron ^{1,*}

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Dissemination

Article

Microbiological and Physicochemical Profile of Traditionally Produced *Chouriça de Carne* Dry-Fermented Sausages: Towards Benchmarking of Products Against Established Quality Groups

Ana Sofia Faria ^{1,2,3}

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Dissemination

Journal of Food, Nutrition and Diet Science

<https://ojs.luminescence.cn/FNDS>

LUMINESCENCE

<https://luminescence.cn/>

Original Research

Technological, microbiological and sensory quality attributes of goat's milk kefir: comparison between plain and flavored types

Mariem Ayed¹, Sana Yakoubi², Vasco Cadavez¹, Ursula Gonzales-Barron^{1*}

¹ CIMO, LA SusTEC, Instituto Politécnico de Bragança, Campus de Santa Apolónia, 5300-253 Bragança, Portugal

² National Institute of Research and Physical-Chemical Analysis (INRAP), Laboratory of Materials, Treatment and Analysis, Biotechpole Sidi-Thabet, 2020, Ariana, Tunisia

Dissemination

Article

Dynamic Modelling of *Listeria monocytogenes* Growth in a Milk Model Medium as Affected by pH and Selected Lactic Acid Bacteria Strains

Yara Loforte ^{1,2}

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Dissemination

applied microbiology

Article

Growth of *Listeria monocytogenes* in Goat's Pasteurized Milk Cheese During Maturation: Its Prediction from a Milk Model Medium

**Yara Loforte ^{1,2}
and Ursula Gonzales-Barron ^{1,*} **

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Dissemination

applied microbiology

Article

Effects of Multifunctional Lactic Acid Bacteria Strains and Kefir Ferment on Microbiological, Physicochemical, Nutritional and Sensory Attributes of Goat Pasteurized Milk Cheese

Yara Loforte ^{1,2}, André Martinho de Almeida ^{3,4}, Vasco Cadavez ¹ and Ursula Gonzales-Barron ^{1,*}

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Dissemination

applied microbiology

Article

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Dissemination

Article

Genetic Characterization of Lactic Acid Bacteria Isolated from Artisanal Alheira - a Portuguese Fermented Meat Sausage

Nathalia Fernandes ¹

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Future work

- ▶ Analysis of LAB's WGS data
- ▶ Three more publications planned relative to WP5
- ▶ Organization of the International Final Seminar PAS-AGRO-PAS “Agropastoralism and products”

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Institut des Régions Arides

Merci pour votre attention

Any question?

